

FACTORING CLIMATE CHANGE INTO MALARIA ERADICATION STRATEGY

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HANNAH NISSAN, ISRAEL UKAWUBA, MADELEINE THOMSON

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- Climate can influence malaria directly, by affecting transmission dynamics through vector and parasite development, or indirectly, via its influence on socioeconomic systems and other processes relevant to malaria infection, control and elimination. Section 1 documents the direct and indirect pathways via which malaria control and elimination strategies may be affected by climate, highlighting where climate data and forecasts could be used to anticipate and manage changing risks
- Despite the complexity of local transmission dynamics, some climate drivers of malaria risk at local scales are closely connected with large-scale, predictable components of the climate system. Climate information has the potential to inform a wide range of decisions related to malaria control through an improved understanding of the following:
 - mechanisms of disease transmission
 - monitoring and evaluation of interventions
 - spatial variations risk
 - temporal variations in risk on multiple time frames (from sub-seasonal to decadal and long-term trends)
- The climate has distinct timescales of natural variability (diurnal, seasonal, interannual, decadal) superimposed onto long-term trends caused by anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions. Climate change will not be felt primarily through gradual trends over long periods of time but through changes in daily weather extremes, seasonality and other components of climate variability. A wealth of research evidence indicates that:
 - long-term trends are more pronounced for temperature than for precipitation
 - local precipitation trends are often not discernible above the background of interannual and decadal variability, though could become more prominent as climate change progresses
 - an eradication strategy which focuses exclusively on long-term trends and fails to recognise natural variability on other timescales could increase vulnerability to climate
- Climate change projections are produced by Global Circulation Models (GCMs), and can be downscaled using regional models to provide projections at local scales for planning purposes. Section 2 discusses the strengths and limitations of climate change (decadal to multi-decadal) projections and provides guidance for their use in decision-making.
 - the forecast skill of climate change projections cannot be quantified
 - uncertainty in climate change projections stems from multiple sources and cannot be quantified reliably
 - climate change projections cannot be taken at face value
 - projections from global models should only be used on continental to global scales for decision-making
 - without a full evaluation of model variability on monthly, seasonal, annual and decadal timescales, model output should be averaged over at least 30 years

- the robustness of predictions from regional models is difficult to assess, and they should not be used in decision-making without a full assessment of their strengths and weaknesses
- expert judgment based on a thorough evaluation of climate model projections for the region, timescale and application of interest can inform a scenario planning approach to climate change adaptation
- An assessment of forecast capability on multiple temporal and spatial scales indicates (Section 2 and Appendix):
 - weather and seasonal forecasts currently offer the most potential for use in decision-making although the former provides little additional advance on observed weather given the natural time lags that occur during the rise of an epidemic.
 - decadal forecasts show some skill at predicting anthropogenically-forced temperature trends, but struggle to predict the natural variability around the trend
 - decadal precipitation forecasts have very poor skill
 - an inverse relationship exists between forecast lead-time and the precision of forecast information in both space and time: longer-term forecasts are generally less specific about when and where we can expect certain outcomes. Averages or aggregations are provided over larger spatial and longer temporal scales as forecast lead-time increases.
- Recommendations (Section 3):
 - once a malaria eradication strategy is developed it should be tested against plausible climate futures
 - a structured approach to the integration of climate into malaria eradication strategies based on the timing and scope of fixed and flexible decision points
 - emphasise flexibility in adaption plans, reinforced by iterative review and management of eradication strategies to incorporate new climate monitoring and forecast information
 - investment in monitoring and surveillance systems for both climate and malaria
 - capacity building in the malaria community to understand and use climate information effectively
 - development of institutional relationships that enable the malaria community to access climate knowledge, data and climate funding
 - research priorities:
 - testing the sensitivity of malaria eradication strategies to plausible changes in future climate to identify key vulnerabilities
 - identification of timescales on which models can be useful in priority regions for the SAG_{ME}
 - evaluation of large-scale drivers of local climate impacts in priority SAG_{ME} areas
 - investigation of methods to depict and communicate plausible climate future scenarios to assist decision-making

- diagnosing the role of climate vs. non-climate factors in the success and failure of previous malaria interventions in order to better-target future efforts

1. WHICH ASPECTS OF CLIMATE NEED TO BE CONSIDERED FOR MALARIA?

Malaria has always been understood as a climate sensitive disease, with transmission historically associated with summer months in temperate zones and humid lowlands in tropical regions. Unusual weather conditions have often precipitated deadly epidemics. A variety of statistical and mathematical models of malaria transmission, driven by climate variables, have been used to explain past cases and predict future incidence. Over the last 20 years models which emphasise the importance of temperature have been used to predict likely changes in the geographic distribution of the disease in a warmer world, all else being equal (Martens et al. 1999). This simplistic approach to explaining the spatial and temporal dynamics of malaria at the global scale is contrasted with that of renowned malariologist, Hackett, who in 1937 said: *“everything about malaria is so moulded and altered by local conditions that it becomes a thousand different diseases and epidemiological puzzles. Like chess, it is played with a few pieces, but is capable of an infinite variety of situations”*. Hackett’s view suggests that little about malaria is predictable. These contrasting perspectives have been at the heart of a protracted debate on the likely importance of climate change to the future burden of malaria relative to other factors such as drug resistance (P Reiter 2008; Alonso et al. 2011; Hay et al. 2002). Identifying just how, where and when climate may be relevant to the malaria eradication strategy means bringing together these two perspectives in a pragmatic way.

Malaria is also a disease of poverty with the poorest often most prone to infection and having the least access to preventive and curative services. High levels of endemic malaria have also been shown to put a break on socio-economic development (Sachs & Malaney 2002), an observation which has been a major motivation for governments and international donors to invest in malaria control and elimination (RBM 2015). Poverty is an outcome of various drivers, some of which are also related to climate. For instance, climatic shocks may impact on livelihoods and drive households below the poverty line.

If we are to understand how climate change may impact malaria eradication activities going forward we need to understand which aspects of the relationship between climate and malaria transmission, morbidity and mortality are predictable at different spatial and temporal scales, from local to global. Climate can influence malaria directly, through its effects on

FIGURE 1 PATHWAYS OF INFLUENCE BETWEEN CLIMATE AND MALARIA

vector and parasite development and malaria transmission dynamics, or indirectly, through myriad pathways including its influence on the many socioeconomic factors that combine to determine malaria risk in the real world (Figure 1). We are therefore compelled to explore the full range of potential risks associated with the enormous environmental, social and economic impacts of climate change which may impact malaria eradication efforts through multiple possible pathways. Some of these pathways are also predictable. For example, seasonal cycles of rainfall drive the agricultural calendar and the patterns of nutritional deficit in poor rural populations associated with the pre-harvest hungry season. Extreme

weather shocks undermine household economies, health service supply chains and ultimately government tax revenues that may be used to provide public services, making populations vulnerable to health shocks. Warming trends in temperate and highland regions not only make transmission of malaria more likely, they can also reinforce transmission in marginal zones, making it harder for control programs to be effective. In addition, climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies may support or undermine malaria elimination and eradication strategies. For example, micro-dams, installed to reduce the impact of drought may result in the creation of vector breeding sites.

Climate provides a number of unique opportunities when compared with other factors impacting on malaria transmission such as co-infection, human behaviour and control efforts. To begin with, climate varies predictably by location according to defined processes. It also has distinct natural cycles, for example diurnal and seasonal, as well as multi-year or decadal variations such as those driven by El Niño and the Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO). Anthropogenic changes are super-imposed on these natural cycles. Climate is also routinely measured (using land and sea observations, satellite-based remote sensing and global modelling outputs), modelled and predicted at multiple space and timescales using structured methods developed by weather and climate experts around the globe. Despite many known weaknesses this highly structured mass of data, stored in national and global repositories, provides hourly, daily, weekly and monthly historical information for most regions of the planet and forms the basis for predictions of the future climate.

1.1. USING CLIMATE INFORMATION FOR DECISION MAKING

Prior work has demonstrated that climate information (see Appendix: Table 3 and Table 4) has the potential to inform a wide range of health decisions (Connor et al. 2010) through an improved understanding of the following:

- **Mechanisms of disease transmission:** to help identify new opportunities for intervention. For example detailed analysis of the role of temperature on mosquito/parasite dynamics has resulted in a better understanding of how climate drives disease (Blanford et al. 2013)
- **Spatial risk:** to help identify populations at risk for better targeting of interventions. Climate is commonly used in the development of risk maps at multiple scales (Hay & Snow 2006; Bennett et al. 2013)
- **Seasonal risk:** to inform the timing of routine interventions such as indoor residual spraying (Grover-Kopec et al. 2006)
- **Sub-seasonal and year-to-year changes in risk:** to identify when changes in epidemic risk are likely to occur to initiate appropriate prevention and response strategies. For example, in semi-arid Botswana malaria epidemics have historically been associated with unusually heavy rains, which are in part predictable (Thomson et al. 2006). The forecasting of such weather anomalies may identify periods when targeted efforts to interrupt malaria transmission could most likely succeed.
- **Trends in risk:** to identify long-term drivers of disease occurrence (including changes in the climate) to plan for and support future prevention and response strategies. For example, warming in Ethiopia has

increased the altitude at which cold temperatures create a natural barrier to malaria transmission (Lyon et al. 2017)

- **Assessment of the impacts of interventions:** to evaluate the role of climate as it enables or limits disease transmission. For instance, a recent analysis of the impact of climate on malaria impact assessment revealed the potential for variations and trends in rainfall and temperature on multiple timescales could result in an under-estimation or over-estimation of malaria intervention impact (Thomson et al. 2017).

FIGURE 2 TANZANIA ENACTS WEIGHTED ANOMALY STANDARDIZED PRECIPITATION (WASP) INDEX USING ENHANCED NATIONAL CLIMATE SERVICES PRODUCTS (BLENDED STATION AND SATELLITE DATA) FOR TANZANIA USING A BASELINE PERIOD JANUARY 1995 TO DECEMBER 1999. BROWN INDICATES TIME WHERE RAINFALL WAS BELOW THE BASELINE AVERAGE, WHEREAS GREEN INDICATES RAINFALL WAS ABOVE THE BASELINE AVERAGE. THE WASP ANALYSIS IS OVERLAID WITH THE TIMING OF INTERVENTIONS DESCRIBED IN DETAIL IN SMITHSON ET AL. (2015) (TAKEN FROM (THOMSON ET AL. 2017)).

The climate naturally varies on multiple timescales (Figure 3), from the daily weather and seasonal cycles to fluctuations occurring from year-to-year (inter-annual variability) and over longer cycles of 10-30 years (multi-decadal variability). This natural climate variability has been superimposed on a background of nonlinearly increasing greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere since around the start of the 20th century, which has led to detectable trends in average climate (particularly temperature), as well as to changes in the shorter-timescales of climate variability such as extreme weather events and seasonality. Given the effects on malaria transmission of changes in temperature and rainfall (Section 1.3) such variations in climate have significant implications for efforts to control and eliminate malaria.

Natural climate variability on different timescales is driven by a range of factors. The atmosphere is a fundamentally chaotic system, meaning that very small perturbations occurring anywhere can lead to starkly different weather patterns (a phenomenon called the butterfly effect). Variations in the strength and position of the sun relative to the Earth drive the daily and seasonal cycles. El Niño, a pattern of surface temperature variability occurring every 2-7 years in the tropical Pacific Ocean, is a strong driver of

inter-annual variability in local climate impacts around the world, particularly in the tropics. Large volcanic eruptions occur sporadically, but can cool the planet by up to about a degree for one or more years. For example, when Mount Pinatubo in the Philippines blew in 1991, it pumped 17 million tons of SO₂ into the atmosphere and caused an approximate 0.6 degrees Celsius cooling effect in the Northern Hemisphere in 1992 and 1993. Slowly varying patterns in ocean temperatures and circulation, including in the deep layers of the ocean, and variations in the sun's activity drive climate variability on the order of decades and longer.

FIGURE 3 TIMESCALES OF VARIABILITY FOR GLOBAL AVERAGE ANNUAL PRECIPITATION (A, MM/DAY) AND TEMPERATURE (B, °C) ANOMALIES. RAW ANNUAL AVERAGES ARE SHOWN IN BLACK, FITTED DECADEAL CYCLES IN GREEN AND THE LONG-TERM TREND IN RED. SEE GREENE ET AL. (2011) OR [HTTP://MBELL.MAPROOMDEV.IRI.COLUMBIA.EDU/MAPROOM/GLOBAL/TIME_SCALES/INDEX.HTML](http://mbell.maproomdev.iri.columbia.edu/maproom/global/time_scales/index.html) FOR METHODOLOGY.

The best-studied example of how the climate interacts with society on multiple timescales is seen in the African Sahel (Hulme 2001). Using 30-year averages before and after 1960, rainfall across the region fell between 20 and 30% (FIGURE 4). Within this period of low rainfall, extreme drought years occurred in 1973 and 1984. The droughts resulted in widespread food insecurity and severe malnutrition, population movement and loss of traditional livelihoods as herds of pastoralists were decimated (Batterbury & Warren 2001). Mortality due to famine was rife. Malaria prevalence rates were observed to decline by greater than 80% in the semi-arid areas of northern Senegal and Niger from the early 1960s to the mid 1990s (Mouchet et al. 1996). The drought and associated land-use change resulted in a loss of vector breeding sites, lower vector survivorship, the loss of the vector species *Anopheles funestus*, and a consequent shortening and reduction in intensity of the malaria transmission season.

Climate scientists have demonstrated that a warming of the tropical Pacific and Indian Oceans, of the order of 0.2°C or larger, is associated with negative rainfall anomalies in the Sahel and that negative rainfall anomalies are accompanied by local land surface warming of up to 0.6°C above average (Giannini et al. 2003). The theory that sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies are the driving force behind the droughts contrasts dramatically with earlier perceptions. Prior to the publication of this critical climate research, responsibility for these regional drought disasters had been put upon the shoulders of local peasant farmers, whose overuse of the land was deemed to have resulted in reduced vegetation cover, the advance of the desert, and localized impacts on the regional climate regime (McCann 1999).

FIGURE 4 TIMESCALES OF VARIABILITY FOR PRECIPITATION (MM/DAY) ANOMALIES IN THE AFRICAN SAHEL. ANNUAL AVERAGES ARE SHOWN IN RED, FITTED DECADAL CYCLES IN BLUE AND LONG-TERM TREND IN BLACK (MASON ET AL. 2015).

The use of climate information on different timescales should be designed to correspond with the time horizons of decision-making (Figure 5) (Thomson & Mason 2018). For example, malaria control practitioners may be interested in ensuring that the malaria control strategy is resilient to climate change but, as they work within a traditional political cycle and with annual budgets, long term climate scenarios are unlikely to be relevant to their immediate decisions. Conversely, national and international policy makers concerned with the development of long term strategies, medical and vector counter measures and research and development may need to take into account the potential impact of warming on the strategies and products they develop.

FIGURE 5 TIME HORIZONS FOR DECISION-MAKING IN THE HEALTH SECTOR (Thomson & Mason 2018)

1.2. MODELLING CLIMATE-MALARIA INTERACTIONS

MODELS OF MALARIA TRANSMISSION

The rate at which malaria may spread through a human population can be captured by the basic reproductive ratio (R_0) (the number of secondary infections produced by an infection in a population that is totally susceptible) and by the generation time (the time between a case becoming infected, and causing other infections) (Breban et al. 2007). For malaria to persist in a population, transmission by the mosquito vector must be efficient enough that, on average, at least one new case arises from each infected individual. This condition is satisfied when the basic reproduction rate, R_0 (an index of malaria stability), exceeds 1.

R_0 is proportional to the duration of infection in the host, the man-biting rate, and the average number of human blood meals an infected mosquito takes after having survived the parasite's extrinsic cycle. Seasonal fluctuations in some or all of these parameters entrain seasonal changes in prevalence in the human host, with a lag that decreases as the annual average R_0 increases. The risk of malaria infection, stability and seasonal patterns of disease transmission are determined by vector abundance, duration of the extrinsic incubation period (i.e. the time it takes from a mosquito getting infected to it becoming infectious) and survival rate of the vector, combined with the probability of the vector feeding on a susceptible human host. These biological parameters are directly influenced by meteorological variables such as rainfall, temperature, and humidity (Macdonald 1952)

A simple vectorial capacity model (Box 1) illustrates where climate variables impact disease dynamics.

BOX 1 CLASSICAL VECTORIAL CAPACITY

Four parameters comprise the classical formula for vectorial capacity (V): the parasite's extrinsic incubation period (EIP, n days); the ratio of mosquitoes to humans (m); mosquito survival through one day (p); and human biting rates (a):

$$V = \frac{ma^2p^n}{-\ln(p)}$$

All biological processes are sensitive to temperature: normally, increases in temperature will speed up associated chemical reactions within certain bounds. For parasites and vectors we identify a degree day threshold below which no activity can occur, an optimum peak and range and a lethal threshold at high temperatures when enzymes are denatured. The extrinsic incubation period of *P. falciparum* has classically been described by $EIP = 111/(T-16)$, where T is the ambient temperature, although detailed laboratory studies and field observations indicate that the relationship is more complex (Paaijmans et al. 2010; Paaijmans et al. 2012). As surface water is needed for the creation of breeding sites, rainfall or other water sources are needed to foster mosquito egg laying and juvenile development. Humidity of about 60% is needed to ensure vector survival sufficient to complete the extrinsic incubation period (time for parasite development) the length of which is determined by temperature. The direct effects of temperature, rainfall and humidity on transmission risk are discussed further in Section 1.3.

CLIMATE-DRIVEN MODELS FOR USE IN MALARIA RISK ASSESSMENTS

The hypothesis that climate change and climate variability are responsible for observed changes in malaria risk has received mixed responses. The impact of climate changes on malaria in the East African highlands illustrates the challenge well. A 1998 study suggested that, given the known relationship of temperature to malaria transmission and with all other factors remaining equal, global warming could result in the geographic spread of malaria transmission into previously malaria-free highland areas (Lindsay & Martens 1998). A highly polarised debate ensued which had, at its centre, an analysis of malaria and climate data from the highlands of Eastern Africa. Based on a number of studies some authors concluded that rising malaria was associated with warming temperatures in the region (Loevinsohn 1994; Pascual et al. 2006), whereas others concluded that the increase in malaria in the highlands was caused by other factors, especially drug resistance (Shanks et al. 2002; Hay et al. 2002). Omumbo et al. (2011) argued that part of the discrepancy in views was due to the poor quality of the climate data used in many of the studies, while Pascual et al. (2008) reported that disease and meteorological factors might complement each other and interact at different time scales. Stern DI et al. (2011) confirmed differences in the climate data sets used but pointed out that, while there is evidence of warming and an increased risk of epidemics, malaria declined around 2005 in the area in association with control efforts. The overall impression was that, at the time, the effectiveness of the available control tools was sufficient to overcome the effects of climate change.

In recent years mathematical models of malaria, of varying degrees of complexity, have been developed both to explain observed variations in cases and to predict future ones (Koella 1991). These mechanistic models can be driven by climate data and can be used to explore likely changes in transmission as a result of variations and trends in the climate (Hoshen et al. 2000; Worrall et al. 2007; Alonso et al. 2011; Tompkins & Volker 2013; Caminade et al. 2014; Ruiz et al. 2014). A study by Ruiz and colleagues (Ruiz et al. 2014), using a series of mechanistic models to explore the predictability of malaria cases at Kericho, indicated a reduction in simulated malaria cases after 2005 based on climate inputs alone. All models are uncertain and understanding sources of uncertainty in the development of climate-driven disease forecasts can help decision-makers understand where, when and why forecasts may be more or less robust. It also allows the prioritization of error reduction. A recent study by Tompkins and Thomson (in prep) used climate information to drive a dynamical model for malaria transmission to simulate observed clinical cases for Kericho in Kenya. In such a model hierarchy, it is useful and usual to separate the total uncertainty into a cascade of uncertainty contributions represented by boundary condition (e.g. climate data), initial conditions (gametocyte carrier rates) and dynamical model uncertainty, with the latter consisting of both model structural and model parameter uncertainties. The authors used a new constrained genetic algorithm to assess the various contributions of model and climate uncertainty to overall uncertainty in malaria-related health outcomes. They found that, in the East African highlands region, uncertainty in the temperature data used was by far the most significant source of uncertainty. Investments over the last 10 years in improved climate data for use in national malaria decision-making have demonstrated the value of reducing this source of uncertainty (Thomson et al. 2017).

1.3. DIRECT IMPACTS OF CLIMATE ON MALARIA TRANSMISSION

We define the direct effects of climate on malaria risk as those pathways affecting the malaria pathogen itself or the host vector through a measurable climate variable. Three variables (temperature, precipitation and humidity) are known to have a direct effect on malaria transmission.

TEMPERATURE

There is considerable evidence that, within moderate temperature ranges, warmer conditions facilitate malaria transmission by influencing both the rate of parasite development and vector population dynamics.

The basic biological response of any organism to temperature is the thermal response curve. This curve may be estimated for a number of different physiological processes occurring in the parasite, the vector or the human host. In the 1990s climate and malaria studies commonly identified the threshold at which parasite development starts, optimum thresholds are reached and lethal thresholds occur through

Extrinsic Incubation Period (EIP) Prediction Curves

FIGURE 6 THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EXTRINSIC INCUBATION PERIOD AND TEMPERATURE (BECK-JOHNSON ET AL., 2013)

laboratory studies of the effects of temperature on development rates of *Plasmodium falciparum* and *P.vivax* in the Asian vector *Anopheles maculipennis* (Craig et al. 1999; Martens et al. 1999).

More recent research has shown that determining the shape and optimum temperature-dependencies of the parasite and vector population are complex, do not correspond with each other, and differ significantly from prior studies (Figure 6 and Figure 7, Beck-Johnson et al. 2013). These authors estimate that abundance of adult female vectors (those responsible for transmission) is greatest between about 20 and 30°C, with an optimum temperature range of 25-27°C. Above about 32°C

reduced adult survival and lower recruitment from juvenile stages of mosquito development cause the adult population of mosquitos to drop sharply. At the other end of the temperature scale, below approximately 18°C, mosquitos do not survive long enough to complete the extrinsic incubation period (the time needed for the parasite to develop in the mosquito). Consequently, transmission at colder temperatures is unlikely.

Most studies examining the influence of temperature on malaria transmission risk have focused on average temperatures, but there is evidence from modelling work, supported by empirical evidence in Kenya (Paaijmans et al. 2009), and laboratory experiments on

FIGURE 7 DIFFERENT APPROXIMATIONS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN POTENTIAL INFECTIOUS VECTOR ABUNDANCE AND TEMPERATURE (BECK-JOHNSON ET AL., 2013).

rodent malaria (Paaijmans et al. 2010) that diurnal temperature fluctuations moderate the temperature-dependence of malaria transmission. Both studies found that diurnal temperature fluctuations increased rate processes of both the malaria parasite and mosquito development at low average temperatures and decreased rate processes at high average temperatures. Stronger effects were observed for a larger diurnal temperature range (from 0°C to 16°C) at low and high average temperatures (Paaijmans et al. 2009). The implication of these findings is that malaria transmission may become possible at cooler temperatures, and may be curtailed in less extreme hot conditions, than has commonly been thought. At the same time, optimum transmission may occur at cooler average conditions than previously supposed. A decrease in diurnal temperature range is one of the markers of climate change, as night-time temperatures have warmed faster than day-time temperatures since the 1950s (Thorne et al. 2016; Easterling et al. 1997). Locally, diurnal temperature range is moderated by urban growth, desertification, irrigation and land-use, and the change has not been uniform across the globe (Easterling et al. 1997). Nor has the decrease been constant with time, particularly on local scales, as positive and negative changes have been observed on interannual and decadal timeframes (Easterling et al. 1997).

Overall, modelling studies have demonstrated the complexity of the temperature influence on overall transmission risk, producing substantially different estimates of optimum temperature for transmission according to the different assumptions about the temperature dependencies and variability of each component.

Different estimates of the transmission thresholds have important implications for understanding future malaria risk in a changing climate. For example, increasing night time temperatures have been observed in recent decades and this trend is predicted to continue in many areas, which could imply greater parasite and mosquito survival outside the usual malaria season in areas exhibiting seasonal malaria risk. Different temperature thresholds may also imply differences in the potential future expansion and contraction of geographic malaria zones. If the optimum and maximum temperature thresholds for transmission are on the lower side of current estimates, more malaria control may be needed in temperate regions, and less in hot areas where conditions may be too hot for malaria transmission. Conversely, if the maximum transmission temperature is closer to upper estimates, rising temperatures could continue to exacerbate malaria risk in already hot regions. Any changes in the future variability of temperature will also have important implications for transmission. In hot regions and/or at the hottest times of the year, when the maximum temperature may already close to the upper threshold, transmission will be limited by an increase in temperature variability. Conversely, increased variability in mean daily temperatures near the minimum temperature threshold would increase transmission risk (Paaijmans et al. 2010).

PRECIPITATION

The primary pathway via which precipitation directly affects the malaria vector is by altering the number, quality and location of breeding sites for oviposition (egg-laying). A secondary pathway is the relationship between rainfall and humidity. As with temperature, the relationship of rainfall to malaria transmission may be complex, the response of an insect vector being conditioned on its thermal response curve. Consequently, malaria transmission depends nonlinearly on the amount of rainfall, as well as on its intensity and on the existence of prior conditions such as drought (Thomson et al. 2005; Shaman & Day 2007). Lag relationships also exist between rainfall and its effect on malaria transmission. Moreover, the

time between episodes of rainfall can result in phase amplification, allowing mosquito populations to grow rapidly, while longer spacing of rains can limit the growth rate of the mosquito population (Shaman & Day 2007). Non-linearities in the relationship of climate drivers to disease outcomes is an important reason for considering the use of mathematical models in climate disease analysis as they are able to capture some of these dynamics using mechanistic models.

Temperature and precipitation do not vary independently from one another; precipitation is usually associated with (at least temporary) reductions in near-surface temperatures. Therefore, while rainfall can enhance malaria transmission through its effect on breeding site abundance and humidity, this effect can be tempered by cooler conditions which may constrain malaria transmission or enhance it, depending on the proximity to critical temperature thresholds for transmission. Parham & Michael (2010) argue that precipitation more strongly controls malaria endemicity than temperature through its influence on vector abundance, but that temperature has a greater influence on the rate of disease spread as long as sufficient rainfall exists to maintain a population of adult vectors.

HUMIDITY

High humidity is essential to mosquito survival as these insects are highly susceptible to desiccation. High humidity may precede heavy rainfall when temperatures are high, since moisture evaporating from the land surface in warm conditions is prevented from escaping by the arrival of clouds. Near the land-surface, high relative humidity leads to an increase in mosquito survival, flight activity and host-seeking behaviour. These changes favour malaria transmission within an optimum relative humidity range of approximately 60-80% (Garg et al. 2009; Haque et al. 2010). In dry areas mosquito vectors seek out humid micro-climates in shady burrows or dark dank corners in houses.

1.4. INDIRECT PATHWAYS OF CLIMATE INFLUENCE ON MALARIA CONTROL STRATEGIES

People's experience of the climate is not determined by average conditions, but by the daily weather, seasons and year-to-year variations in temperature, rainfall and other climate variables. Consequently, the gradual, long-term trends in climate, which have been observed in recent decades and are predicted to continue in the future, are not the means by which people will experience most aspects of climate change. Instead, it is primarily through changes in the daily weather (including weather shocks such as catastrophic storms), seasons and potentially through alterations to longer-term components of climate variability, such as the El Nino Southern Oscillation or decadal shifts, that society will feel most of the impacts. Understanding how climate variations across these different timescales may affect disease management strategy is an essential starting point to addressing if and how potential future changes in the climate should be considered.

Climate variability and change have many complex ramifications for socioeconomic systems and other processes relevant to health management. Many of these indirect effects are understudied and unquantified, but an understanding of the potential pathways of influence and the manner in which they may materialize can inform the design of a successful long-term malaria eradication strategy by ensuring it is robust to a range of plausible, though uncertain, outcomes.

This section discusses the indirect pathways via which the climate could impact upon malaria eradication efforts and how potential future changes in the climate may become relevant. The impacts of climate variations on different time frames are unpacked separately, from short term to long term (extreme weather, seasons, interannual to decadal climate variability and climate change trends). In fact, it is impossible to truly separate out the different timescales of climate variability, because long-term changes affect the statistics of variability in the shorter-term. For example, the acceleration or stagnation of warming in decadal cycles will be accompanied by changes in the frequency and intensity of heat and cold waves. Longer-term trends due to rising greenhouse gases are superimposed on these decadal fluctuations, especially for temperature, and are already affecting weather variability. Cross-cutting issues related to malaria control with more complex climate pathways are discussed at the end of the section.

EXTREME WEATHER EVENTS

Extreme weather and climate events include storm surge, hurricanes, heat and cold waves, heavy rainfall and flooding. These events all occur on timescales of hours up to a week or two. Detecting changes in the frequency of extreme weather events is challenging because of a lack of data and the rarity of such events means that statistical significance is difficult to achieve. Nonetheless, changes in the frequency and severity of some types of extreme weather have already been detected, including heat waves and, in some regions and for some seasons, heavy rainfall (Hartmann et al. 2013). Overall, global precipitation is expected to increase, but regional changes will vary substantially; some areas may see increases while others experience less rainfall. Among the most robust predictions for the future climate are an increase in frequency of heat extremes (and a decrease in cold extremes) (Collins et al. 2013).

- **Logistics** One of the primary effects of extreme weather is disruption to the normal functioning of society. The practicalities of accessing diagnostics, drugs, vector control and vaccines become particularly challenging during periods of extreme weather. Roads and other transport lines may be out of service, complicating the transport of supplies and personnel, and compromising access to vulnerable populations, especially in remote rural areas. Among other factors, extreme climate and weather shocks can cause people to be either temporarily or permanently displaced, and subsequently hinder access to vulnerable populations.
- **Supply chains** As supply chains become increasingly monopolized, the continued provision of key commodities such as vaccines, drugs and ITNs becomes more vulnerable to disruption, both from climate shocks and non-climate factors like political unrest. Furthermore, the increasingly global nature of commodity supply chains means shocks occurring around the world could affect the continued supply of medical and preventive equipment for malaria control.
- **Vector control** Pooling water following periods of rainfall generally increases the availability of suitable breeding sites, but in some cases heavy rainfall has been observed to reduce vector abundance by flushing out and diluting existing sites. The nonlinearity of these mechanisms means that changes to the frequency, intensity and location of extreme rainfall episodes may have unpredictable effects on overall malaria transmission. In addition, skilful forecasts of extreme precipitation with sufficient lead time to enable preparatory action are difficult to achieve, particularly with precise information about the likely location of rain.

- **Behavioural factors** Changes in the frequency and severity of heat waves may also impact malaria control through behavioural factors. Excessive heat, particularly during the dry season, is a common barrier to the use of insecticide-treated nets (ITN) (Watanabe et al. 2014; Binka & Adongo 1997) and may facilitate resurgence of malaria in some settings.
- **Vaccine supply** Though not an immediate concern, maintaining the ‘cold chain’ for vaccine supply is likely to be threatened by extreme weather if a malaria vaccine (currently in pilot implementation) is deployed widely in the future. Power outages and interruptions to normal storage and transport protocols during disruptive weather can break the cold chain (Scott & Macisaac 2004; Yakum et al. 2015). During heat waves, such breaks rapidly expose vaccines to high temperatures, particularly in tropical developing countries where power supply is already often intermittent.

SEASONALITY

Changes in the optimum season for malaria transmission could occur in the future, for example through a lengthening of the high transmission season as temperatures increase or a change in the timing (or the interannual variability in timing) of seasonal rainfall patterns. There is some agreement that monsoon seasons may become longer with climate change in many regions (Christensen et al. 2013). Shifts in seasonality may affect the impact of malaria control programs and require a change in the timing of operations, such as Indoor Residual Spraying (IRS) of insecticides. Risk mapping may become less effective as changes in seasonality deviate from historical patterns used to inform baseline risk analyses. One modelling study suggested that the malaria season in the Sahel may get shorter (Ermert et al. 2012), though such studies are highly uncertain and suffer from the many limitations described in Section 2. Changes in seasonality should be monitored carefully and, where skilful, seasonal and sub-seasonal forecasts could be used to appropriately time interventions such as seasonal drug administration and IRS.

INTERANNUAL CLIMATE VARIABILITY

Variations in climate from year to year can manifest in changes in seasonal total rainfall or average temperature, the number of extreme weather events in a year or season and the onset or cessation timing of seasonal climate patterns (e.g. dry/rainy seasons). While changes in weather patterns and variability have already been observed with increasing anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions, there is no evidence of increasing interannual variability over recent decades, although some modelling studies

Changes in some weather patterns have already been observed, but confidence in future changes in interannual and decadal climate variability is low. Weather and seasonal forecasts, reinforced by an understanding of historical variability in the climate drivers of malaria risk, can be used to develop an adaptive malaria control strategy.

indicate that changes in interannual variability could occur in the future (Collins et al. 2013). Increased interannual variability has been projected in summertime European temperatures, arctic sea ice extent and regional precipitation associated with the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) (Collins et al. 2013; Christensen et al. 2013). However, confidence in predictions of any change in interannual variability is low because models

currently fail to adequately capture both the variance and spatial pattern of ENSO, the dominant mode of interannual variability in the climate system (Christensen et al. 2013).

Drought is an extreme case of interannual rainfall variability. Defined as a climate shock (as opposed to a weather shock), drought has a slower onset and a longer duration than extreme weather phenomena like heavy rainfall or heat waves. Less rain normally lowers the risk of malaria. However, drought conditions have also been associated with an abundance of breeding sites, as drying river beds and streams leave stagnant pools of water suitable for oviposition (Thomson et al. 2005). There is evidence of a particularly strong link between rainfall and malaria following drought periods, particularly in semi-arid areas (Thomson et al. 2005; Connor et al. 1999). In Botswana reduced prevalence of malaria during the drought of the early 1980s resulted in a lack of preparedness, high case numbers and fatalities when normal rainfall returned in 1988 (Thomson et al. 2005).

Management of the effects of interannual climate variability on malaria incidence therefore requires an adaptive management strategy to stay on top of dynamic risks. Seasonal forecasts (where skilful (Figure 14)), reinforced by an understanding of historical variability in the climate drivers of malaria risk from year to year, can help anticipate changes in malaria risk. Close monitoring of weather forecasts can be used to anticipate and prepare for extreme rainfall or heat waves during particularly wet or warm years.

DECADAL CLIMATE SHIFTS

Monitoring variability in the climate drivers of malaria risk on 10-20 year decadal cycles can help to anticipate where resurgence or elimination of the disease may be particularly likely. Human (and political) memory tends not to extend much further than the past ten years. Failure to recognize where recent patterns could in fact arise from decadal shifts and not from longer term climate change trends could lead to outbreaks if authorities are unprepared for a potential reversal in background climate suitability.

Separating out the contribution of slowly-varying background changes in climate from other drivers of malaria risk would help (a) to improve upon monitoring and evaluation of malaria programs and (b) anticipate an optimal period to push for elimination. Effective disease control efforts have been shown to have masked the influence of decadal temperature variability on malaria incidence in East Africa, which otherwise would have predisposed the region towards increased risk of outbreaks (Chaves & Koenraadt 2010). The example of the decline in Sahel rainfall and subsequent droughts during the 1970s and 1980s (see Section 1.1) illustrates the importance of recognizing the role of decadal climate variability in complex health and agricultural systems.

Research and development timelines for medical and vector counter measures are of the order of 5-20 years. Product stability in higher temperatures (and associated shifts in temperature extremes) may merit consideration in product development.

CLIMATE CHANGE TRENDS

Two notes of caution are needed to interpret the literature projecting malaria transmission risks into the long-term.

1. The complexity of factors, beyond climate, which contribute to malaria incidence are not accounted for in studies of the effects of climate on malaria (Chaves & Koenraadt 2010; Paul Reiter 2008). Similarly, the effects of climate are not considered in models incorporating, for example, host immunity and malaria control efforts. The observation that malaria has been both absent from areas with environmental conditions conducive to transmission and present in areas unsuitable for parasite transmission reiterates that climate is far from the only control on malaria risk and models which integrate both climate and social factors are needed (Chaves & Koenraadt 2010). A study of malaria transmission in northern Europe, where outdoor temperatures were commonly below known transmission thresholds, found that the disease persisted in the cold climate by means of summer dormancy of hypnozoites in humans and indoor transmission of sporozoites throughout the winter by semi-active hibernating mosquitoes (Huldén et al. 2005). Researchers studying trends in malaria in Africa over the past 115 years could not explain the overall decrease in prevalence of the *Plasmodium falciparum* parasite over this period by either climate or disease control interventions (Snow et al. 2017).
2. Modelling studies projecting the exact location of malaria transmission zones years into the future (e.g. Ermert et al. (2012); Leedale et al. (2016)) suffer from the limitations of predicting long-term climate described in detail in Section 2. Such studies can be useful for a broad ‘horizon-scanning’ exercise but are highly uncertain, especially at local scales and in mountainous regions, and should be interpreted with caution. In one such study, a large ensemble of climate model simulations suggested a warmer and wetter East African Community region (Leedale et al. 2016). Two different malaria models forced with the output from the climate model ensembles both suggest greater sensitivity of malaria to temperature than to precipitation changes, and predict an increase in transmission at higher altitudes and a reduction in lowland, marginal transmission zone where excess heat inhibits transmission.

It is impossible to truly separate out the different timescales of climate variability, because decadal shifts and climate change trends are accompanied by corresponding changes in shorter-term climate and weather variability.

Without knowledge about the magnitudes and precise locations of uncertain climate trends, we can nonetheless consider how some long-term changes might influence malaria control strategies. In most cases, the strongest influence of climate on disease risk will occur on shorter timescales, but long-term trends could have important consequences in some areas:

- The expansion and contraction of climatically-suitable malaria zones would be relevant for all components of a malaria control and eradication program, potentially requiring a scale-up of new disease control efforts in previously unaffected areas and review of resource allocation in newly eliminated areas. One of the most robust predictions in this area is the expectation that the

altitude at which malaria transmission is possible will increase with global warming, exposing non-immune populations in new highland areas to risk of the disease. At a certain altitude, the decrease in temperature with elevation causes the minimum temperature limit for parasite survival to be crossed, providing a natural barrier to malaria outbreaks. With increasing temperatures, the elevation at which this minimum temperature limit is reached will increase, expanding the zone of malaria risk to higher altitude regions. Lack of sufficiently long data records on malaria incidence, vector control programs and local climate have so far confounded efforts to discern the influence of long term climate trends on malaria prevalence in the historical record.

Separating out the contribution of climate from other drivers of variability in malaria risk across multiple timescales would help

- a. to improve upon monitoring and evaluation of malaria programs and
- b. anticipate an optimal period to push for elimination.

These efforts are further hindered by the nonlinearity both of the climate trends themselves (which makes delineating between decadal cycles and long-term trends challenging) and of the malaria response to changes in local climate. A recent study on the Ethiopian highlands confirmed

that the elevations of minimum transmission thresholds have indeed been increasing, but also found considerable interannual and spatial variability in these thresholds, stressing the importance of understanding local climatic constraints on shorter timescales as well as variations in climate trends on the local scales at which malaria control programs are implemented (see Box 2) (Lyon et al. 2017).

- In regions where long-term trends assist elimination, residual transmission may become a more important component of an eradication strategy.
- Coastal intrusion caused by slowly rising sea-levels and brief storm surges may influence vector species in unknown ways, but is most likely to suppress transmission.
- Upward trends in the concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere may have chemical effects on malaria risk, separate from their effects on altered climate and weather patterns. Elevated concentrations of carbon dioxide may be linked to delayed larvae development and increased mortality in woodland areas through an alteration in the chemical and nutritional quality of leaf litter (Rier et al. 2005).
- Trends in atmospheric CO₂ may also affect the nutrition of staple crops, with consequences for malaria morbidity and mortality (see the discussion on nutrition below).
- Rising CO₂ concentrations increase rates of plant growth. Although this plant fertilisation effect provides a slow benefit to agricultural productivity, which may indirectly influence malaria control and eradication through many indirect socioeconomic effects, it must be balanced against the complex and more immediate effects of changing weather patterns, seasonality and longer-term variability

CROSS-TIMESCALE EFFECTS ON ERADICATION EFFORTS

Residual transmission As efforts to control malaria improve and the goal of eradication draws closer, residual transmission following earlier successful control programs is likely to become a key focus. Risk

mapping to identify transmission hotspots (areas where climate and other factors make local transmission feasible) can be more efficient than disease surveillance in low transmission areas and may help to target interventions appropriately (e.g. by determining if malaria cases may have been locally acquired or imported from nearby regions) (WHO 2016). The features of transmission hotspots may change in response to shifts in the character and variability of the weather, as well as climate variations on longer timescales. Knowledge of how within-season variations in climate suitability, not just longer term or monthly average temperature and rainfall, influence transmission risks would assist these efforts but is hampered by a lack of quality data and insufficient case numbers in low transmission areas and seasons (Cohen et al. 2013).

Insecticides There is mixed evidence about the influence of temperature on the sensitivity of mosquitos to insecticides (Soko et al. 2015). Some studies report a decrease in mosquito mortality at higher temperatures (Patil et al. 1996; Raghavendra et al. 2010; Glunt et al. 2014), while others report an increase (Polson et al. 2012). Overall, the research reveals a complex resistance response, depending on the type of insecticide and the range of temperatures tested (Glunt et al. 2014; Whiten & Peterson n.d.). Possible effects of changing climate and weather patterns on insecticide efficacy are therefore difficult to discern. Further research would be needed to identify any important thresholds, and to investigate whether insecticides are affected differently by slow changes in ambient temperature (for example a warmer-than-usual season) or rapid heat and cold waves, factoring in any timelines in insecticide toxicity that may mediate the influence of temperature.

Disease surveillance sites are essential for identifying changes in patterns of disease risk (on all timescales) and to enable and effective and timely responses, particularly on the borders of transmission and in areas of cyclical low transmission.

Health systems Well-functioning and adequately funded health systems in endemic countries are rare. Health systems are vulnerable to climate in a number of ways.

1. Population Access

- Extreme weather and climate events cause disruption to the logistics of operating a functioning health system, making it difficult for staff to reach work, for supplies to be transported and for people to access health care.
- As transmission dynamics evolve over time, in part influenced by climate, the constitution of vulnerable groups may change and health systems must respond accordingly. For example, regions transitioning from endemic to epidemic will need to address a shift in susceptible age groups from children under 5 years to people of all ages (WHO 2016).
- Changing livelihoods, migration patterns and urbanisation are influenced by environmental change and bring new challenges to which health systems must respond to ensure that vulnerable populations can be identified and accessed (see Box 3).
- Depressed household incomes following weather shocks, particularly in communities heavily dependent on agriculture, may prevent people from seeking medical attention when needed.

BOX 2 CONNECTIONS BETWEEN GLOBAL AND LOCAL CLIMATE

Despite the complexity of local climate, in many regions of the world variations in local climate conditions are clearly connected with large-scale, predictable patterns of variability in the oceans. The close correspondence between interannual variations in minimum elevation thresholds for malaria transmission in Ethiopia with the occurrence of El Niño and La Niña events is evident in Figure 8. Correlations between sea-surface temperatures in the tropical Pacific Ocean and the elevations of the 15°C and 18°C thresholds in the highlands were 0.73 and 0.62, respectively (Lyon et al. 2017). Even on a global scale, temperatures over land are more variable than in the oceans, but they nonetheless track closely with ocean temperatures on interannual and longer timescales (Figure 9).

FIGURE 8 CHANGES IN THE ELEVATION THRESHOLD FOR MALARIA OVER TIME IN THE ETHIOPIAN HIGHLANDS. THE SOLID LINES DEPICT TIME SERIES (1981 - 2014) OF THE MEAN ELEVATION ABOVE MEAN SEA LEVEL (M) WHERE THE DEKAD (10 DAY) AVERAGE MINIMUM TEMPERATURE IN A GIVEN CALENDAR YEAR NEVER EXCEEDS 18°C (RED) AND 15°C (BLUE). DASHED LINES AROUND BOTH CURVES INDICATE THE UNCERTAINTY IN MEAN ELEVATION. COLORED BARS SHOW ANOMALOUS VALUES (°C) OF THE OCTOBER – DECEMBER “NIÑO 3.4” SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE INDEX. TREND LINES FOR EACH SERIES AND THEIR ASSOCIATED SLOPES ARE ALSO SHOWN (TAKEN FROM LYON ET AL. (2017).

FIGURE 9 THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LARGE-SCALE LAND AND OCEAN TEMPERATURES AND LOCAL CLIMATE AND MALARIA INCIDENCE IN KERICHO, KENYA. EL NIÑO AND LA NIÑA EVENTS, DEFINED BY PERIODS OF WARM OR COOL SEA-SURFACE TEMPERATURES IN THE TROPICAL PACIFIC OCEAN, ARE INDICATED AT THE BOTTOM OF THE FIGURE. MONTHLY CASES OF MALARIA ARE INDICATED IN SOLID LIGHT BLUE, CORRESPONDING TO THE RIGHT-HAND AXIS (TAKEN FROM THOMSON ET AL. (2011)

2. Government funding

- Currently, governments of endemic countries fund 32% of malaria control activities, with health systems constituting nearly 90% of government expenditure (WHO 2016).
- Climate change is expected to depress economic productivity, particularly in developing countries (see Cross-Cutting Issues below).
- As the economic impacts of climate change materialize, funding for malaria control will likely be squeezed during times of economic hardship. Funding for health services, including malaria control, may be particularly hard-pressed following extreme weather and climate shocks that cause a drop in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and tax revenues.
- The effects of malaria on GDP cannot be separated from the impact of poverty on malaria risk (Malaney et al. 2004). Malaria outbreaks also exert a financial toll on national economies, though estimates of this cost vary widely, from as little as 1% to as much as 50% of GDP.

Increased vulnerability to malaria could therefore have an amplifying feedback on malaria incidence via its economic impact on national productivity and government expenditure.

CROSS-CUTTING ISSUES

Climate change adaptation Climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies may support or undermine malaria elimination and eradication strategies. For example, the use of DDT as a pesticide in agriculture to improve production led to benefits for public health, but may have contributed to insecticide resistance in Zimbabwe (Soko et al. 2015). Increased irrigation or the installation of micro-dams as protection from drought could influence malaria transmission. Migration and subsequent policy-responses to shifting migration patterns could also impact health systems through population access.

Climate variability and change have ramifications for socioeconomic systems and other processes relevant to health management, many of which may be too complex to predict.

Water management Water management practices evolve in response to climate stresses and market forces and can have unintended consequences for malaria transmission. In areas of unstable malaria transmission where local communities lack immunity, for instance in the African highlands and desert fringes, widespread irrigation to improve agricultural yields increases the number of mosquitos and can lead to an increase in malaria incidence. However, in areas of stable transmission (most of sub-Saharan Africa) there is no evidence that irrigation impacts transmission rates. Despite an increase in mosquito density with irrigation, malaria risk may decline due to substitution with a mosquito of lower vectorial capacity which thrives in more irrigated land. In either case, improvements in the local economy as agricultural incomes grow and stabilize with irrigation generally lead to better ITN use and improved access to healthcare services compared with communities not using irrigation (Ljumba & Lindsay 2001).

Nutrition Food insecurity and nutrition are affected by climate variability on multiple timescales. Famine is always the result of a myriad of factors, but drought is usually a precondition. Climate and weather shocks that suppress agricultural production can drive up food prices and contribute to malnutrition. In Bangladesh, an increase in food staple prices was observed to occur following major floods that destroyed rice yields, with impacts on the proportion of underweight children seen the following year (Thomson et al. 2015). Rising atmospheric CO₂ has also been linked with a decrease in the nutritional quality of plants, as staple crops grown at elevated CO₂ concentrations have been found to contain reduced amounts of iron, zinc and (for non-legumes) protein (Myers et al. 2014; Loladze 2014). The effect of malnutrition on malaria depends on the level of food deprivation. Refeeding famine victims can increase malaria, depending on the amount and type of sustenance given, while in chronically malnourished, but not starving, populations protein-energy-malnutrition may increase malaria morbidity and mortality (Shankar 2000). Nutritional supplementation to manage malaria risk could become a more important component of malaria control in the future in response to increased food insecurity and changes in nutrition related to climate change, but more evidence of the effects of supplementation is needed (Shankar 2000).

Economic productivity Climate change is expected to depress economic productivity, but the magnitude of this impact is strongly contested. The Stern Review predicts a 5-20% loss in global GDP (Stern 2006), though critics claim these estimates are too high (Tol 2006). However, there is consensus that the least developed countries are likely to shoulder most of these economic costs. The high dependence of developing countries on agriculture, a highly climate-sensitive industry increases their susceptibility to climate shocks (Novta et al. 2017). These economic impacts are expected in response to both changes in weather shocks and slower trends. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) shocks can follow extreme weather and climate events through a suppression of agricultural productivity, reduced worker efficiency (e.g. during heat waves), and deterioration in the health of the working population (which can be driven or exacerbated by lower investment in health services when tax revenues are low). Compensatory changes and their effects on GDP growth may be slower, such as the adaptation of economies to specialize in new industries (e.g. green technology), or diversification to reduce dependence on industries susceptible to climate and weather.

Studies examining rates of malaria incidence during times of economic shock or change are lacking, but there is evidence of a connection between the rapidity of transition in the economy (whether boom or bust) and overall mortality rate, though these studies suffer from poor data availability and continuity (Stuckler et al. 2009; Leon & Walt 2000). In post-Soviet countries, the pace of change during the 1990s left governments unable to manage health systems. A rise in disputes and conflict, reduced access to health care and a decrease in job security during times of economic hardship were among the causes of increased mortality and depression of life expectancy during this period (Leon & Walt 2000). Economic downturns can also affect nutrition, though in inconsistent ways (Stuckler et al. 2009). There is strong evidence of the relationship between the price of staple foodstuffs, which can be impacted by economic shocks, and nutritional metrics such as underweight, stunting and wasting. When the price of rice is high, less money is available to purchase non-staple foods and this directly impacts nutrition (Christian 2010; Matthys et al. 2006).

Political unrest, conflict and war The pathways of causality between climate and conflict are nuanced and run in both directions (Von Uexkull et al. 2016). Drought and other climate shocks can exacerbate tensions and competition for resources, especially in poor, agriculture-dependent communities, making conflict more likely when other pre-conditions exist (Von Uexkull et al. 2016; Türk et al. 2015). Climate shocks are also felt more strongly in conflict situations as vulnerability is high and services and coping abilities are limited (World Food Program 2012). Food insecurity, often associated with drought or flooding in the context of war and civil unrest, is a common part of this picture. Adverse climate and weather effects on food security have been documented in ten major conflict areas (Afghanistan, Burundi, Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of Congo, Iraq, Somalia, Sudan, Syria and Yemen), where approximately 53.5 million food insecure people were estimated to be affected (World Food Program 2012).

In conflict zones, forced displacement is common and complicates the delivery of basic health services. In Yemen, fuel shortages have disrupted the delivery of medical supplies and there is a lack of available healthcare personnel. A deterioration in sanitation and availability of clean water increases the risk of

infectious diseases. Vector control and disease surveillance programs are not operating effectively, and power outages have made it difficult to maintain the cold chain for vaccines. There has been a rise in the number of malaria cases, particularly among internally displaced persons (World Health Organisation 2016)

“The concurrence of conflict and climate-related natural disasters is likely to increase with climate change, as climate change not only magnifies problems of food insecurity and nutrition, but can also contribute to a further downward spiral into conflict, protracted crisis and continued fragility.” (World Food Program 2012).

BOX 3: MIGRATION, URBANISATION AND LIVELIHOODS UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE

“Increased large scale migration to urban centres is inevitable due to the global realities of aging societies, slow and uneven economic growth among regions in a country and among nations, and environmental and climatic instability” (IOM 2015)

Most **migration** which occurs in response to extreme climate and weather is internal within the affected country and involves temporary movement across short distances between rural areas, or from rural to urban settings (IOM 2015). Though extreme weather receives most attention, gradual environmental change and slow onset events like drought have a greater impact on the movement of people (Laczko & Aghazarm 2009). Most migration is now to **urban centres**, and most future population growth is expected to occur in cities. The African urban population has been growing at an unprecedented rate for decades (IOM 2015).

Projections of the impacts of climate change on migration are highly uncertain (Türk et al. 2015; Gemenne 2011), but natural hazards and disasters are a driving force behind displacement (Türk et al. 2015). Climate change alone is unlikely to cause people to move, but may contribute to an increase in vulnerability, making it more challenging for people to survive in their current setting (IOM 2015). This increased vulnerability could be caused, for example, by reduced agricultural productivity due to drought and environmental degradation, or increased competition for natural resources (Gemenne 2011; Laczko & Aghazarm 2009).

The high vulnerability of agricultural incomes to weather and climate can encourage **livelihood diversification**, which may cause people to migrate or change existing migration patterns. Seasonal migration to facilitate multiple livelihood sources have been observed in several countries including Mali, Senegal and Ethiopia (Laczko & Aghazarm 2009). Mobility is a natural coping strategy to environmental change, but increases in extreme weather events can make this type of temporary migration less feasible. Climate change may turn choices into necessities as environmental pressures intensify and hard coping limits are reached (Gemenne 2011). In parts of Southeast Asia and sub-Saharan Africa, normally temporary migration patterns have become permanent moves in response to livelihood pressures from environmental shocks.

HOW WILL CHANGING MIGRATION PATTERNS AFFECT MALARIA ERADICATION?

- Populations displaced by force generally have poorer access to health services and suffer from undernutrition, food- and water-borne illnesses, overcrowding and other problems which could make malaria control and eradication more challenging (Smith et al. n.d.).
- Urban populations are generally healthier than rural communities. City-dwellers have better nutrition, vaccine coverage, access to health services and better use of ITNs (Hay et al. 2005).
- Mosquitos thrive less well in cities, as fewer open spaces for breeding and more polluted waters reducing the cleanliness of existing breeding sites. Vector survival, biting and malaria infection rates are lower than in rural areas (Hay et al. 2005). The difference in transmission between urban and rural areas is greater in wet than dry regions: in general, wet regions are more likely to be endemic, with higher transmission rates, than dry (usually epidemic) regions. The benefit of urbanization in terms of reduced malaria transmission may therefore be greatest in wetter, endemic areas.

2. INTERPRETING DECADAL TO MULTI-DECADAL CLIMATE MODEL PROJECTIONS

2.1. SOURCES OF UNCERTAINTY IN CLIMATE PREDICTION

Uncertainty in climate prediction on all timescales comes from:

1. Initial conditions: the current state of the climate
2. Boundary conditions: external drivers of the climate system
3. Model uncertainty
4. Natural climate variability

As in the framing for malaria modelling described in Section 1.2, uncertainties in modelling the climate system can be traced to initial conditions, boundary conditions and model uncertainty. In addition, natural climate variability must be considered as an additional source of uncertainty. Although the definition and relative importance of each of these components varies, they are common to weather and climate prediction on all timescales (Table 1).

The **initial conditions** for generating a climate forecast are provided by current observations of the climate system. Data are collected using a range of observing systems, including weather stations, satellites, ships and unmanned instruments which descend into the deeper layers of the ocean. However, even with improvements in observing systems over recent decades, these measurements are incomplete, particularly in the deep oceans. Sparse observations from disparate sources are assimilated using physical models which interpolate among data to give a gridded, three-dimensional approximation of the state of the climate system. Measurement error, flaws in the assimilating model and the limited resolution of the resulting dataset contribute to uncertainty in the initial conditions from which a forecast is initialised.

Boundary conditions refer to processes that drive the evolution of the climate system for the duration of the forecast but are included as independent variables in the forecast system. The simplest boundary condition included in all forecasts is the daily and annual solar cycle. In the long term (from several years to several decades), projected anthropogenic greenhouse gas and aerosol emissions and land cover changes from, for example, human-influenced desertification, land-use change and deforestation, also drive the climate system and have to be approximated as boundary conditions. Four 'Representative Concentration Pathways' (RCPs), transient scenarios describing the plausible external forcing of the climate throughout the coming century, have been constructed based on assumptions about economic, technological, demographic, population and policy evolution over the coming years (Moss et al. 2010). The RCPs are not forecasts or policy recommendations, but should rather be treated as plausible future development scenarios. Without further information, we cannot assume that one RCP is more likely than another. That said, monitoring of greenhouse gas emissions since the RCP scenarios were devised in 2005 already suggests that we are not on course to follow the RCP scenario with the least external forcing of the planet (RCP2.6), though it is possible that drastic policy measures or technological leaps (for example) could lead us to change course in the future.

Model uncertainty arises from the failure of climate models to perfectly simulate the response of the climate system to the driving boundary conditions, as well as its natural variability in both space and time. Such problems stem in part from the compromises struck in the name of computational efficiency, for instance decisions to exclude or simplify certain components of the climate system like ice sheet dynamics, stratospheric chemistry or cloud processes, and approximations of the fundamental dynamical equations (i.e. based on physics) made when the models are coded. Parameterization, the representation of small scale processes not resolved at the resolution of the models (e.g. clouds and feedbacks between land surface and atmosphere), contributes significantly to structural model uncertainty. While climate models are undoubtedly useful as tools for understanding, and have been shown to capture key physical processes and represent climate variability on some timescales, for some regions and variables, studies have demonstrated considerable problems with the models' ability to capture key elements of the climate system, such as clouds, extreme precipitation, certain aspects of monsoonal systems and even the basic seasonality of variables in some locations. In general, models perform better on larger scales, but struggle to capture the climate and weather on smaller regions, particularly at the scale of the model grid.

Dynamical (based on the laws of physics) and statistical (based on empirical relationships estimated from historical data) climate models can be used to 'downscale' global model output to provide information at smaller spatial and temporal scales. Multiple steps are needed to downscale global projections (Figure 10) and each step adds assumptions and approximations, introducing further layers of uncertainty to an already complex picture (Trzaska & Schnarr 2014). Even after downscaling, data are still gridded and have not been calibrated for use in local decision-making. The consequences of model uncertainty are discussed in greater detail in Section 2.4.

Natural climate variability

Beyond weather lead-times (up to about 2 weeks) climate predictions provide information about aggregated conditions over a period of time. The longer the lead-time, the greater the length of the aggregation period. For example, seasonal forecasts may provide average temperature and total precipitation over a three-month period. Decadal predictions provide forecasts of average temperature or total rainfall over several years. Averaging across any time period smooths out the natural weather and climate variability occurring on shorter timescales. Seasonal forecasts ignore weather variability (though seasonal forecasts are now being developed for the frequency of wet spells or heat waves expected over the course of a season). Decadal forecasts smooth out interannual variations. Long-term climate change projections may provide useful information about the average climate over a 30-year period in the future, but cannot predict the timing of decadal (and shorter term) variability (see Section 2.3). It is therefore very important to consider climate variability occurring on shorter timescales when making decisions based on long-term climate information.

2.2. HOW CLIMATE PROJECTIONS ARE MADE

Figure 10 illustrates the process of generating a climate change projection. First, assumptions about global socioeconomic development are made to generate scenarios of future greenhouse gas and aerosol emissions. Global climate model simulations are produced for each of these emissions scenarios, using a

range of different models. Finally, projections are developed at regional and local scales using either dynamical or statistical models, or a combination of both.

The global climate system is modelled using general circulation models (GCMs). GCMs are constructed on a 3-dimensional grid covering the surface of the Earth, which extends into the deep ocean and up into the atmosphere. The resolution of the model is described by the grid size, which is typically about 100-500 km², though computational advances are improving resolution all the time. In each grid, the models use fundamental laws of physics to compute the basic evolution of the climate system, determining the wind circulation, pressure and density, water vapour and temperature. Only one value of each variable is produced for each 100-500 km² grid. The effects of processes occurring at unresolved sub-grid scales (e.g. clouds, turbulence, radiation processes, carbon chemistry) on the system must be approximated using functional relationships (a process called parameterization). Weather features on smaller scales than the resolution of the models, for instance thunderstorms, local rainfall and flooding and local weather in mountainous regions, are not captured. Because of the coarse spatial scale of global climate models, they cannot be used to infer information about local climate, and on temporal scales shorter than monthly averages (Trzaska & Schnarr 2014).

Information is often required at smaller spatial and temporal scales than can be provided by global models, to assist with local, national or super-national decision-making. Output from global models can be “downscaled” dynamically (using a regional climate model (RCM)) or statistically (using statistical relationships determined from historical observations). Dynamical regional climate models take the large-scale climate fields provided by the global models as boundary conditions and use the same fundamental laws of physics to simulate the local climate on a grid of (approximately) 10-50 km².

FIGURE 10 STEPS AND COMPONENTS INVOLVED IN GENERATING CLIMATE CHANGE PROJECTIONS. GCM: (GLOBAL) GENERAL CIRCULATION MODEL; RCM: REGIONAL CLIMATE MODEL (TAKEN FROM DANIELS ET AL. (2012)).

2.3. DECADAL TO MULTI-DECADAL CLIMATE PROJECTIONS

Due to the chaotic nature of the atmosphere, uncertainty in weather prediction is dominated by initial conditions uncertainty. Such forecasts are limited to lead times of about two weeks. However, the climate, which describes the prevailing conditions over a longer period of time, does not suffer from this limitation to the same extent, and can be predicted with some skill at a range of lead times. Initial conditions are still important for climate prediction, but gradually diminish in significance with increasing lead time.

The decadal (2 to 9 years) to multi-decadal (10 to approx. 30 years) timeframe, which together can be termed *near-term climate*, is a particularly challenging problem in climate prediction, and a forefront of research efforts. Interannual to decadal variability is superimposed on long term trends about which models show considerable disagreement. Near-term climate change is a transition time frame: these lead times combine the difficulties of seasonal and long-term climate change predictions, as both initial conditions and externally forced trends are important (see Table 1).

Two types of predictions are produced for the near-term climate:

1. Uninitialized model projections (<https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/cmip5/>)
Developed by the Coordinated Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5)
 - Run out to centennial lead times
 - Several different climate models are run to generate a multi-model ensemble for a variety of anthropogenic emissions scenarios. The multi-model ensemble average is calculated in an attempt to cancel out some of the problems in the different models.
 - Used for IPCC assessments
2. Initialized decadal forecasts from the Decadal Climate Prediction Project (<https://www.wcrp-climate.org/dcp-overview>)
 - Produced for lead times of 2-9 years
 - These forecasts use a subset of the same models used for the CMIP5 simulations

Accurate prediction of near-term climate change requires forecast systems to capture both the trend and the natural decadal variability around the trend. The key difference between the two types of near-term climate predictions is that the initialized decadal forecasts attempt to capture the natural decadal variability as well as the anthropogenically forced trend. The initialised predictions start from current observations of the climate and predict how the system will evolve from there, while the uninitialized CMIP5 projections do not account for the current state of the climate. The uninitialized projections also simulate natural variability, but without initialization the timing of the cycles does not match the real world, so they cannot be used to forecast the timing of cycles. The multi-model ensemble average smooths out the natural decadal variability simulated by each model, and therefore only captures the climate change trend. Therefore, the natural variability around this trend is an additional source of uncertainty in these projections, and must be factored in if they are to be used effectively in decision-making.

Near-term climate prediction skill has only been assessed for lead times of up to a decade. Skill estimates vary substantially among models, studies and skill score metrics, but positive skill has been demonstrated for temperature over the oceans and some land areas, though not at the local levels desired for the majority of planning decisions. Precipitation skill is generally poor, with a few exceptions in the high latitudes (Figure 13). Comparisons between initialized and uninitialized predictions reveal that almost all decadal forecast skill comes from predicting the trend due to external anthropogenic forcing; the forecasts do not capture the variability around the trend very well (Figure 13). Initialization of decadal forecasts has led to only modest, and inconsistent, improvements in skill up to approximately 5-8 years (Goddard, a. Kumar, et al. 2012). Difficulties estimating the initial conditions (especially in the deep oceans) and failure of models to fully capture the physical processes leading to decadal variability could be responsible for the limited improvement obtained by initialisation. At present therefore, forecast systems show some skill at predicting long term temperature trends, but struggle to predict the natural variability around the trend (Goddard, A. Kumar, et al. 2012; Doblus-Reyes et al. 2013; van Oldenborgh et al. 2012).

Decadal forecasts show some skill at predicting anthropogenically-forced temperature trends, but struggle to predict the natural variability around the trend. Decadal precipitation forecasts have very poor skill.

In general, regions where the externally forced trend is strong and decadal variability is a relatively small component of the total variability show better skill than regions where trends are weak or decadal variability is large (Meehl et al. 2014). Temperature trends are generally much stronger than precipitation trends, and are more discernible above the background of climate variability on shorter timescales (FIGURE 4 and Figure 11). The strength of the temperature trends partly explains why decadal prediction skill for temperature is so much better than for rainfall.

Natural decadal variability and climate models are the main sources of uncertainty in projections of near-term climate change. Divergence in anthropogenic emissions scenarios only becomes really important after the first few decades.

Because of a lack of data for verification (see Section 2.4), no skill assessments are available beyond the first decade. The limited benefits of initialization are lost in the first 5-8 years, after which decadal variability continues to be a major source of uncertainty in predictions of near-term climate change. Model uncertainty also causes substantial spread among predictions on these lead times and throughout the 21st century, for both temperature and precipitation and at all spatial scales. It is not until several decades from

now that uncertainty about the trajectory of future anthropogenic emissions causes projections to diverge substantially and the relative importance of natural variability is diminished compared with other sources of uncertainty (Hawkins et al. 2009; Hawkins & Sutton 2011). However, for precipitation at smaller physical scales (regions and sub-regions), natural variability remains an important source of uncertainty throughout the coming century.

The relative strength of the temperature trends compared with decadal variations suggests that the temperature predictions may continue to show some skill over the next several decades. However, precipitation is more variable in both space and time than temperature, and is less well simulated by climate models (Flato et al. 2013). Most precipitation variability occurs on interannual timescales. Long term trends are often less pronounced than for temperature, and are undetectable over the observational record in many areas. On the regional and local scales of most interest for societal impact, decadal fluctuations in precipitation can be significant (Figure 11). In these areas, climate projections are likely to be less accurate. On a global scale, model uncertainty is the greatest source of disagreement among precipitation forecasts throughout the coming century, illustrating both the limitations of the current generation of climate models and the potential for improvement in coming years. Compared with temperature, future emissions have little bearing on precipitation predictions, especially on regional scales and over the next few decades. (Hawkins & Sutton 2011).

Long-term trends are more pronounced for temperature than for precipitation. Local precipitation trends are often not discernible above the background of interannual and decadal variability, though could become more prominent as climate change progresses.

FIGURE 11 PERCENT OF TOTAL VARIANCE (%) IN ANNUAL MEAN PRECIPITATION (A,C,E LEFT) AND TEMPERATURE (B,D,F RIGHT) EXPLAINED BY THE LONG-TERM TREND (A,B TOP), DECADAL (C,D, MIDDLE) AND INTERANNUAL VARIABILITY (E,F, BOTTOM). BASED ON 20TH CENTURY MONTHLY MEAN TEMPERATURE AND PRECIPITATION DATA (SEE [HTTP://IRIDL.LDEO.COLUMBIA.EDU/MAPROOM/GLOBAL/TIME_SCALES/](http://iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu/maproom/global/time_scales/) FOR INFORMATION ON DATASETS AND METHODOLOGY).

Timescale of variability	Time frame	Drivers	How drivers are measured	Dominant sources of uncertainty for prediction	How forecasts are evaluated
Weather	Hours to 2 weeks	Chaotic atmosphere; previous weather patterns	Meteorological observations; numerical model analysis; satellites	Initial conditions in the atmosphere (butterfly effect)	Full forecast verification against weather observations using expired operational predictions and retrospective predictions (hindcasts)
Seasonal	3-12 months	Earth's orbital position drives basic seasonality; sea surface temperatures (especially those associated with ENSO) drive the evolution of a particular season this year	Sea surface temperature; numerical weather analysis; satellites	Initial conditions in the ocean, model uncertainty	Retrospective predictions (hindcasts), but limited by lack of long time series of historical observations for verification; general evaluation of the physical processes and the temporal and spatial variability captured by models
Decadal	2-9 years	Sea-surface and deeper ocean temperatures (e.g. ENSO and Atlantic variability); anthropogenic forcing; solar variability	Sea surface temperature measurements; deep-sea buoy measurements; numerical model analysis; satellites; modelled scenarios of future anthropogenic forcing	Initial conditions in the ocean; model uncertainty	General evaluation of the physical processes and the temporal and spatial variability captured by models
Multi-decadal	10-30 years	Sea-surface and deep ocean temperatures; anthropogenic forcing	Modelled scenarios of future anthropogenic forcing (currently only uninitialized predictions are made)	Model uncertainty; initial conditions in the ocean (to a lesser extent)	Boundary conditions (anthropogenic forcing); model uncertainty
Century	> 30 years	Anthropogenic forcing	Modelled scenarios of future anthropogenic forcing	Boundary conditions (anthropogenic forcing); model uncertainty	General evaluation of the physical processes and the temporal and spatial variability captured by models

TABLE 1 TIMESCALES OF VARIABILITY AND THEIR DRIVERS IN THE CLIMATE SYSTEM, SOURCES OF UNCERTAINTY AND METHODS FOR FORECAST EVALUATION.

2.4. FUNDAMENTAL PROBLEMS WITH CLIMATE CHANGE PROJECTIONS

Structural model problems

Section 2.1 explained the sources of model uncertainty that contribute to climate prediction uncertainty. Here we describe in more detail some of the consequences of this model uncertainty. Climate models have been evaluated across many criteria, and have been shown to reproduce many important aspects of the climate system. The global warming trend prevalent since the early 1900s, and the subsequent acceleration in warming since the mid-20th century, is well captured by most models. Many of the key spatial temperature patterns, as well as large scale features of some important weather patterns such as the storm tracks and extratropical cyclones, are also represented. However, systematic problems in temperature are found in some regions including, for example, those with high topography. The negative trend in diurnal temperature range over land areas is smaller in the models than in observations, likely because the models do not simulate cloud and land-surface processes well (Lewis et al. 2013). Precipitation remains a significant modelling challenge and a major research priority, as models still fail to capture some key features of large-scale rainfall patterns (Flato et al. 2013).

There are limited studies evaluating the temporal variability generated by climate models. Average global and large scale (hemispheric) temperature variability on interannual to centennial timescales is well captured by most models. Some important modes of variability on sub-seasonal to interannual timescales are represented, including ENSO among others. However, some key features remain poorly captured, including decadal modes in the Atlantic Ocean that are important for near-term climate prediction. Biases in the physical processes needed for accurate simulation of monsoons and ENSO persist (Flato et al. 2013). For example, the CMIP5 ensemble shows a steady warming trend in sea-surface temperatures in the Eastern Pacific Ocean, while no trend has been evident over this period in the data, with serious implications for modelling future El Nino events and their impacts around the world (Lyon & Vigaud 2017).

The results of these evaluations all pertain to large-scale features of the climate system, on continental to global dimensions. On sub-continental scales, and certainly at the regional to sub-national levels of most interest to policy-makers, model performance is significantly worse. Thorough evaluation of climate models on these spatial scales is lacking, as is an understanding of their ability to reproduce key components of temporal variability relevant for decision making on more local scales. In many developing countries data have inadequate temporal and spatial coverage to properly evaluate the models.

Global model projections should only be used on continental to global scales for decision-making. Output from global models should not be used to make decisions based on weather variability or climate shocks, and should always be averaged over at least monthly timescales (Trzaska & Schnarr 2014). Without a full evaluation of model variability on monthly, seasonal, annual and decadal timescales, model output should be averaged over at least 30 years.

Regional climate models (dynamical downscaling models) have been shown to add value to global models through better representation of the spatial features of climate in regions with complex topography, for weather extremes and mesoscale features. They are successfully used for weather prediction, because on those lead times the uncertainties can be fully quantified and the forecasts properly calibrated. However, regional models inherit the biases of the global model they are downscaling, as well as adding their own problems. For climate prediction from years to decades ahead, such models can lead users into an ‘overconfidence trap’: detailed high-resolution maps produced from these models give the impression of high confidence in local climate change impacts decades in advance. If we could quantify the uncertainty in a given global model prediction, subsequent downscaling using a regional model would add spatial and temporal detail to that prediction which could prove useful. In reality (for reasons described in the remainder of this section), the probabilistic long-term predictions cannot be properly quantified, so we do not know how likely those forecasts are to be realized. Multiple steps are needed to statistically or dynamically downscale global projections (Figure 10) and each step adds additional assumptions and approximations (Trzaska & Schnarr 2014). The lack of coordinated comparisons among regional models means that they have not been systematically evaluated in similar depth to global models (Flato et al. 2013). Assessing confidence in regional model predictions is therefore even more challenging than for global models.

Despite these flaws, some robust statements can still be made about the future impacts of climate change impacts on more local scales. Where localized predictions are supported by physical understanding, and in cases where the observational record already shows evidence of local changes that corroborate predictions, we can place more confidence in those forecasts. Examples include the more rapid warming of cities compared with surrounding rural areas.

Downscaling projections using regional models provides information at higher spatial and temporal resolution than global models, but the robustness of these local predictions is difficult to assess. They should not be used directly in decision-making without a full assessment of their strengths and weaknesses.

A wider concern is whether models which have been developed and tuned to perform in the historical climate can be trusted to perform in the future, which will see levels of greenhouse gas emissions that are unprecedented in the recent historical record over which models have been evaluated. Many of the models have been tested on paleoclimate conditions that mirror some features of the current climate and of expected climate change. In the models’ favour, the evolution of the climate system on scales larger than the resolution of the climate models is described by basic laws of physics, which will remain unchanged. However, everything occurring below that resolution (currently ~100km), including for example carbon chemistry and localized heavy rain storms, is based on functional relationships that attempt to capture how the large-scale climate influences the atmosphere on smaller (ultimately microscopic) scales. These functional relationships have been tuned to represent the stationary climate of the past, and cannot be guaranteed in the future. Moreover, while some evaluation of the models has been possible during earlier geologic epochs, the proxy data sources used for these comparisons do not enable evaluation at the local scales of most interest for planning and policy-making.

Forecast validation: quantifying skill

The utility of a forecast depends on its skill. Skill is measured by the extent to which a forecast outperforms another reference forecast strategy, most commonly taken to be the average climate (called the 'climatology'). A forecast produced without an estimate of its skill leads to overconfidence in the forecast and could encourage poor decision-making. Decision-makers would do better to assume the future climate will follow climatology than to trust an unskilled forecast.

Obtaining statistically significant skill estimates requires a large sample of forecasts of past climate conditions ('hindcasts') and observations for comparison and calibration. Such efforts are hampered by a lack of long term observational datasets, particularly in the global south where data coverage is poor. The longer the lead time of the forecast, the longer the required length of the time series of observations and hindcasts. Since initial conditions for decadal climate prediction are provided by slowly varying ocean fields, many decades are needed in order to adequately sample these initial conditions. Moreover, certain situations can enable improvements or lead to deterioration in skill. For example, seasonal forecast skill is significantly enhanced during positive and negative phases of the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO), as fluctuations in the equatorial Pacific Ocean act as large-scale predictors of seasonal climate patterns around the world. There is evidence that decadal prediction skill may be similarly conditional, but this conditionality further stretches the requirement for longer data series for statistically significant skill estimation. Moreover, even if sufficiently long observational time series were available, the non-stationarity of the changing climate means that calibration functions developed for decadal forecasting systems from past data may no longer be appropriate in the future.

The skill of long-term climate projections cannot be quantified. Only thorough model evaluation can be used to judge the quality of this information.

Though available decadal predictions have not been recalibrated, their skill has at least been estimated. Beyond a decade, however, model predictions have neither been recalibrated, nor can we make statements about their skill. Instead, confidence in predictions further ahead must be gaged from model *evaluation*, whereby the physical processes simulated by the models, and their ability to represent key features and aspects of climate variability, are assessed against observations. Model evaluation can only deliver qualitative conclusions about the value of the different model predictions of future climate (see Table 1).

Forecast validation: quantifying uncertainty

Probabilistic forecasts quantify our level of confidence in a given outcome. The mayor of an ocean-front city may hesitate to commit resources to updating flood defences given a forecast that storm surge in 2025 has an 8% probability of reaching some critical level. A probability of 35% might cause the mayor to reconsider. Effective decision-making is extremely challenging without knowledge about the likelihood of a given prediction.

Probabilistic forecasting works by producing multiple model simulations and sampling the full range of prediction uncertainty across the ensemble of model runs. The spread of predictions in the ensemble gives an indication of the prediction uncertainty and outcomes are assigned probabilities according to their frequency among model runs within the ensemble. A crucial final step involves the verification of forecasts against past observations so they can be recalibrated in order to represent the true prediction uncertainty. This step ensures that the probabilities are *reliable*, which means that the predicted probability for a certain outcome is the same as the observed frequency of that outcome. Unreliable probabilistic predictions can be extremely misleading for decision-makers (Vizard et al. 2005).

For weather forecasts, initial conditions are the dominant source of uncertainty, so ensembles of model runs are produced using slightly perturbed initial conditions for each run, which we know (from observations) result in a range of outcomes that satisfactorily capture the true observed range. For multi-annual to multi-decadal forecasts, capturing the full range of prediction uncertainty in an ensemble is much more challenging. A representative ensemble must include a range of initial climate conditions, emissions scenarios and models. Furthermore, the much longer time series of data and past forecasts that would be needed to recalibrate a decadal forecast ensemble presents a significant challenge. Initial attempts to recalibrate decadal forecasts (2-9 years) have resulted in loss of skill and recalibration of forecasts further than a decade into the future is not currently possible.

In fact, the full spread of available climate models may well under-sample the range of model uncertainty. We cannot safely assume that a multi-model ensemble captures all possible responses of the climate system to greenhouse gas forcing, because these predictions cannot be fully validated against observations. Moreover, multi-model ensembles used for the IPCC assessments include all models, with no discrimination based on model performance. The cross-pollination of ideas in the climate science community means that models have not been developed independently and therefore share many components. The implication of this shared architecture is that two models which agree on a certain prediction should not necessarily increase our confidence that it will come true. Estimating the additional uncertainty introduced through using regional models to downscale global model output to the local scale would involve prohibitive computational costs and, as such, these estimations have never been undertaken in a systematic and comprehensive way (Flato et al. 2013). Plausible future emissions scenarios are developed based on assumptions about different future policies, technological progress and population projections, with differences among scenarios leading to substantial spread in predictions for long-term climate change.

Climate change forecasting is a *deep uncertainty* problem: probabilities of different outcomes cannot be quantified reliably. Instead, expert judgment based on scientific understanding can inform scenario planning using climate change projections.

The Coordinate Model Inter-comparison Project (CMIP) ensemble, used for the IPCC assessments, samples some of the many sources of uncertainty, but it can never sample the full range because, as

outlined here, we do not know the true range of uncertainty and, even if we did, it would be computationally unfeasible to generate enough model runs to sample this range in its entirety. Neither the width nor the shape of a future probability distribution estimated from such an ensemble can therefore be relied upon for quantitative probabilistic predictions. Recognizing this problem leads us to acknowledge that predicting the climate beyond verifiable timescales is a ‘deep uncertainty problem’: one where probabilities cannot be assigned to different outcomes. This fact has been widely recognised in the scientific literature (Solomon et al. 2007; Hazeleger et al. 2015; Smith 2002) In a deep uncertainty problem, prediction confidence can only be subjectively assessed with thorough evaluation of the capability of the models to reproduce past climate variability and to represent key physical processes.

Despite recognition that climate change prediction beyond verifiable timescales is a deep uncertainty problem, it has become standard practice to treat the range of climate model projections as an indication of the range of possible outcomes, and to interpret the relative frequencies of different outcomes within the ensemble as their probability of occurrence. The possibility of outcomes not captured by the range of model simulations is generally not addressed. This practice is prevalent both in the scientific literature and in stakeholder-driven settings where detailed information is in high demand.

2.5. IMPLICATIONS FOR DECISION-MAKING

This discussion has outlined the uncertainties inherent in long-term climate prediction. However, these uncertainties do not preclude many robust statements about future climate change (Table 2). Global climate model projections are most robust on continental to global scales and averaged over several decades. Predictions supported by physical understanding are more reliable than those taken directly from climate models without further evaluation. Finally, when accompanied by thorough model evaluation on the relevant spatial and temporal scales for decision-making, model projections can be used effectively to assist with long-term planning.

Why we are not certain	Why we are not ignorant
Incomplete data	Climate models are based on fundamental physical laws
Imperfect models	Models broadly mirror reality on large physical and temporal scales
Uncertain future emissions trajectories	Some predictions have already come true
Future predictions cannot be verified	

TABLE 2 THE STATE OF THE SCIENCE

POTENTIAL PITFALLS

This discussion has highlighted two primary considerations associated with forecasting climate on the near-term climate timeframe relevant for the Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication (SAG_{ME}): climate variability on decision-appropriate timeframes for the variable and location of interest; and understanding the limitations of climate predictions. Failing to address either of these issues can give decision-makers a false impression of confidence and encourage adaptation decisions that could increase, rather than reduce, vulnerability.

An example situation arises in East Africa, where climate model projections are diametrically opposed to recent trends observed over the last 15-20 years. An abrupt reduction in early season (March-May) rainfall since 1998/9 has led to a string of devastating droughts and humanitarian crises (FEWS NET 2011). At the same time, CMIP5 projections indicate increased rainfall in the region over the coming century (Figure 12) (Collins et al. 2013). This so-called climate paradox provides an example of the dangers of both pitfalls highlighted in this report: failure to consider the different timescales of climate variability and an overconfidence in climate model projections.

FIGURE 12 (A) DIFFERENCE IN MARCH-MAY RAINFALL (MM/MONTH) BETWEEN 1999-2010 AND 1977-1998 (B) MULTIMODEL MEAN CMIP5 CHANGE IN MARCH-MAY RAINFALL (MM/MO) FOR 2035-2050 MINUS 1970-2000 (LYON & VIGAUD 2017)

Assuming for the moment that the climate model forecasts for a wetter East Africa are robust, the paradox can be resolved by understanding the long-term trends in the context of climate variability on shorter timescales. Analyses of SST and rainfall observations, supported by controlled model studies, have concluded that the recent decline in East African precipitation is the result of decadal variability in the Pacific Ocean (Lyon & Vigaud 2017). The recent drying does not necessarily preclude a longer-term wetting trend. However, adaptation initiatives motivated by climate model projections could leave the region more vulnerable to shorter term climate changes and shocks. Assumptions for crop-development around long-term rainfall may result in cropping varieties that are ill-suited to drought. Conversely, disinvestment from malaria control based on recent droughts will be short sighted given the possibility that rains will return.

An eradication strategy which fails to recognise climate variability around long-term trends could increase vulnerability to climate.

The second pitfall relates to the validity of the CMIP5 model projections. Closer examination of the CMIP5 ensemble reveals that the models fail to capture some features of the global and large-scale oceans that are critical for simulating East African rainfall. For example, the warming of the Eastern Pacific simulated by models is not matched by observations, which show that warming has so far been confined to the Western Pacific. If the Eastern Pacific begins to warm in line with model projections, rainfall may indeed increase over the coming century in East Africa. If, however, the differential warming between Eastern and Western Pacific persists, the expectation would be for more drought in the future (Lyon & Vigaud 2017). Standard practice would assign confidence in the CMIP5 prediction based on the number of models which agree. A more nuanced assessment of confidence incorporates thorough model evaluation and physical understanding, and in this particular case would conclude that we cannot currently tell whether East Africa will be wetter or drier in the future.

WEATHER, SEASONS AND INTERANNUAL VARIABILITY IN THE FUTURE CLIMATE

Climate-sensitive outcomes in most sectors, including health, are primarily driven by variability in weather and climate on the order of days, weeks, seasons and years. Climate change will influence not only the average state of the climate in the long term, but is also expected to feed back onto our daily experience of the weather through changes in the frequencies and magnitudes of extreme events like heat and cold waves, droughts and extreme precipitation.

Very little is known about how climate change may impact seasonality or interannual variability. Furthermore, the vast majority of research evaluating climate models has focused on long-term climate averages and trends. Evaluation of climate variability in the models, on timescales of relevance for decision making, has not been prioritized. Studies which predict changes to the seasonality or interannual variability of climate in the future should therefore be interpreted with caution and treated as plausible scenarios rather than accurate predictions for planning purposes.

Skilful seasonal prediction has been widespread since the 1990s, building on earlier discoveries about the role of El Niño as a predictor for seasonal climate and weather around the world. It is not known how the strength or nature of these connections may change, and studies have revealed that models do not reproduce them well in the present climate (Flato et al. 2013). Moreover, if the nature of these connections change, forecasts built on statistical relationships between large scale predictors and local climate and weather may no longer be robust.

3. RECOMMENDATIONS

3.1. LONG-TERM PLANNING OF MALARIA ERADICATION STRATEGIES

In order to identify climate-related risks to malaria eradication activities and the potential value of climate information to reduce those risks, a timeline of key activities for the eradication strategy along with soft- and hard-wired decision flexion points must first be developed.

BEGIN WITH MANAGING SHORT-TERM CLIMATE RISKS TO CONTROL AND ELIMINATION ACTIVITIES

Most practical planning decisions in the health sector have time horizons from days to a few years (Figure 5). This decision timeframe means that uncertainty about near-term climate change is best managed by constructing plans which focus on coping with shorter term risks on weather, seasonal and interannual timescales, making use of historical data on climate variability and forecasts on lead times for which they are demonstrably skilful.

FLEXIBLE ADAPTATION PLANS

Flexible adaptation plans would enable the incorporation of decadal forecasts as the quality of this information improves and forecasts become operationally available. Flexibility is particularly important in regions where decadal variability is strong (Figure 11).

ITERATIVE REVIEW AND MANAGEMENT OF MALARIA ERADICATION STRATEGIES

Flexible plans can be iteratively updated to reflect new information about climate changes to date and their health impacts on decision-relevant timeframes, such as changes in seasonality (Hess & Ebi 2016). An effective adaptation plan would focus on managing seasonal and interannual variability, while incorporating real-time monitoring from climate and malaria surveillance systems to assess how longer-term changes could be mediating the efficacy of intervention efforts. This approach is a lower risk strategy than committing resources based on long-term predictions whose skill and reliability is unknown.

PLANNING FOR DECADAL VARIABILITY

Decadal forecasts are not widely available at present, nor are they yet recommended for operational use. However, there is potential for advancement on decadal lead times (2-9 years) in the near future, with tentative estimates of operational forecasts becoming available in the next 5-10 years (Meehl et al. 2014).

In regions where decadal variability is strong, monitoring the climate can help identify decadal-scale cycles. Patterns of change over recent years should be interpreted with caution, as these cycles could reverse in the near future. Where the long-term temperature trend is prominent over the noise of variability on shorter timescales we may expect this to continue, but should be aware that decadal variability could slow the rate of warming. Though global average temperatures will continue increasing in the future, the rate of global warming itself is not linear and can stagnate at any time, as indeed occurred during the 'global warming hiatus' between about 2000 and 2010.

LONG-TERM INVESTMENTS

Climate projections at multi-decadal lead times, in particular those at local scales, cannot be taken at face value. In rare cases where non-flexible planning and investment are needed on very long-term time frames, particularly where precipitation is concerned, we recommend that the key messages from Section 2 regarding the use of global and regional climate projections be adhered to:

1. Global climate model projections should only be used on continental to global scales for decision-making.
2. Output from global climate models should not be used to make decisions based on weather variability or climate shocks, and should always be averaged over at least monthly timescales. Without a full evaluation of model variability on monthly, seasonal, annual and decadal timescales, climate model output should be averaged over at least 30 years.
3. Despite the availability of probabilistic climate change projections, estimates of the uncertainty in these forecasts are unreliable, and skill has not been demonstrated beyond the first 5-8 years.
4. Climate change projections should be regarded as plausible futures, to be used for scenario planning to identify potential vulnerabilities in current action plans.
5. In all cases a climate scientist should be consulted to fully understand the strengths and limitations of predictions for the timescale and location of interest.

The expectation of continued warming trends, with accompanied intensification of heat extremes, is more reliable and should be factored in to long-term research and development activities. However, the precise location and timing of important changes (e.g. reaching key temperature transmission thresholds in new regions, or possible changes in seasonality) are uncertain and should not be calculated from climate model output.

3.2. OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVING MALARIA CONTROL AND ERADICATION WITH CLIMATE INFORMATION

INCORPORATION OF CLIMATE INTO MONITORING AND EVALUATION OF MALARIA CONTROL EFFORTS

Knowledge about the role climate may have played in specific malaria outbreaks will help to understand when and how malaria control efforts are effective and better target these strategies to achieve maximum public health benefit.

INVESTMENTS IN MONITORING AND SURVEILLANCE SYSTEMS FOR CLIMATE AND MALARIA

To enable this knowledge base to be built, investments are needed in both malaria surveillance and in climate and weather observing systems. These improved surveillance systems are needed both within current malaria zones and in peripheral regions to identify areas of emerging risk. Climate observations are particularly lacking in large areas of Africa (Figure 18). The ENACTS (Enhancing National Climate Services) initiative circumvents this problem by combining quality-controlled data from national observing networks with rainfall estimates from satellites, incorporating elevation and reanalysis temperature products. The result is a high-resolution gridded dataset within national repositories, incorporating the best available climate data from different sources. Derived products can then be made available for use in decision-making (Dinku et al. 2016; Dinku et al. 2014).

CAPACITY BUILDING AND PARTNERSHIPS

Capacity building is needed among malaria policy-makers and practitioners in the use of climate information for malaria decision-making. Fostering partnerships between climate and health communities will facilitate the development and uptake of high-quality, fit-for-purpose datasets for use in health-policy decision-making

IDENTIFY SPECIFIC CASE STUDIES THAT PROVIDE RELEVANT EVIDENCE FOR THE SAG_{ME}

Examples of the effective, and less effective, use of climate information for malaria control provide valuable learning opportunities for the SAG_{ME}.

In analysing these case studies, particular consideration should be given to how these examples might be scaled up. Initial countries for investigation might include highland countries in eastern Africa, as well as exploring case studies in other regions bordering temperate zones. Low hanging fruit would include i) an analysis of prevalence data in Ethiopia and the extent to which altitudinal variations in the temperature threshold for transmission are reflected in the epidemiological data 2) analysis of the impact of sea level rise on transmission in the Solomon Isles and 3) changes in malaria prevalence in semi-arid regions in Asia in response to changes in rainfall, irrigation and increasing temperatures.

INVESTIGATE GLOBAL CLIMATE ADAPTATION FUNDS

Global climate adaptation funds, such as the Green Climate Fund, might provide fruitful opportunities to support the development of climate services for malaria eradication.

3.3. RESEARCH PRIORITIES

Climate-proofing the malaria eradication strategy of the SAG_{ME} should begin with an assessment of the vulnerabilities of existing plans to climate variability and change. Identifying and reducing these vulnerabilities will ensure that plans are robust to uncertainty by avoiding the more common approach of tailoring decisions to specific (and highly uncertain) projections of future climate change.

Analyses of climate variability and change in specific areas and on relevant timescales can then be conducted. Confidence in future climate predictions can only be assessed through thorough model evaluation, focused on understanding the timescales and locations for which models perform well and, conversely, where they fail. To place trust in future predictions, it further needs to be demonstrated that when models do succeed, they do so for the right reasons, by capturing the appropriate physical processes and large-scale drivers of local impacts. Such assessments require bespoke analyses targeting specific regions and applications, and cannot be shortcut through a one-size-fits-all approach. The example for East Africa presented in Section 2.5 illustrates the pitfalls of an off-the-shelf method.

The following specific research activities are recommended:

- Testing the sensitivity of current malaria eradication strategies to plausible changes in future climate (including potential expansion of malaria zones) to identify key vulnerabilities
- Identification of timescales on which models can be useful in priority regions for the SAG_{ME}
- Evaluation of large scale drivers of local climate impacts in the climate models, focusing on priority SAG_{ME} areas

- Investigation of methods to depict and communicate plausible climate future scenarios developed through the model evaluation methods described above
- Diagnosing the role of climate vs. non-climate factors in the success and failure of previous malaria interventions in order to better-target future efforts. Clear demonstration of impact is also critical to justify continued funding of specific malaria control strategies.

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APPENDIX

SOURCES OF CLIMATE INFORMATION

Origin of data	Dissemination of data	Advantages	Limitations	Relevance to EWS coverage and context	Timeliness of information
Locally available ground observations from synoptic stations	National archives and monitoring services of the NMHS	National coverage of actual measurements using WMO criteria. Local knowledge of data management helps quality control	Data restricted by NMHS policies – need data access agreement. Data may not be quality controlled and some may be missing.	Only relevant for specific localities in vicinity of station. If large numbers of stations available can provide significant national coverage.	Data relayed routinely in near real time to local or national level can be incorporated into local or national EWS. Data available within 0-1 day of collection
Globally available ground observations from synoptic stations	GTS ¹ run by the WMO ²	Freely available actual measurements of observed rainfall Hourly or daily.	Small percentage of the station data at the national level. Data may not be quality controlled and some may be missing.	Only relevant for specific localities in vicinity of GTS station. If large numbers of stations available can provide significant national coverage.	GTS data are updated in near-real time therefore suitable for EWS at specific locality. Data available within 0-1 day of collection.
Global gridded ground observations	Derived gridded rainfall and temperature products often from GTS but may also access other historical data sources. eg WorldClim ³ UEA-CRU ⁴ , GPCC ⁵	Freely available usually monthly data.	Quality dependent on number, spatial distribution and quality of ground observations which may vary overtime and the statistical methods used to grid the data. Representativeness for an area can be improved if data are aggregated in both space and time.	Often Pan African coverage. Information relevant for large scale impact analysis – e.g. at the provincial, country or regional level.	Not available in near-real time therefore not available for EWS
Satellite data	Satellite-based rainfall and temperature estimates (some combine satellite and limited station data from GTS) e.g. ARC ⁶ CHIRPS ⁷ , CMAP ⁸ , TAMSAT	Freely available. Provides a good approximation of the spatial distribution of rainfall and temperature at the country or sub national level.	Tends to under-estimate rainfall extremes. Representation of actual rainfall at local scale is made difficult by complex topographies, coastlines and inland lakes. Association with actual rainfall may vary throughout the year and by region.	Pan African coverage. Has high spatial and temporal resolution – e.g. 10km and 10 day. Results improved with data aggregation in space and time and with calibration and addition of ground observations.	Available in near real-time and can be used subnational and national EWS. Data aggregated over 10 days and available 1-3 days after collection.

¹ Global Telecommunication System² World Meteorological Office³ <http://www.worldclim.org>⁴ University of East Anglia Climate Research Unit⁵ Global Precipitation Climatology Center⁶ Africa Rainfall Climatology⁷ Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station data⁸ Climate Prediction Center Merged Analysis of Precipitation (ACPC 2011)

Satellite-based land surface temperature estimates from MODIS ⁹ used to estimate minimum and maximum temperature	Freely available. Provides a very good approximation of spatial pattern of temperature variations at local level	If calibrated with station data provides estimate of minimum temperature. Maximum temperature not well represented. Correlation with actual temperature may vary throughout the year and by region.	Pan African coverage. Has high spatial and temporal resolution – e.g. 250m and 16 day. Results improved with data aggregation in space and time and with calibration and addition of ground observations and elevation.	Can be used subnational and national EWS.	Satellite-based temperature estimates available in near-real time (i.e. 16 day summary available 2-4 days after aggregation).
Reanalysis data	ERA-40 ¹⁰ , ERA – Interim ¹¹ , MERRA ¹² model output	Freely available. Not suitable for use in malaria impact assessment without incorporation of extensive local ground station data	Poor representation of quantity and spatial distribution of rainfall; Good representation of minimum and maximum temperature at national and sub-national scale.	Pan African coverage.	Not available in near-real time therefore not suitable for EWS.
Blended product – combining quality controlled national archive with best available satellite products.	ENACTS (Enhanced National Climate Services) ¹³ disseminated by the NMHS	Suitable for analysis at national, sub-national and local level. Images and analysis tools available on NMHS website, data available based on agreement.	Limited number of countries – Ethiopia, Tanzania, Madagascar, Rwanda (although others in process include Mali, Ghana, Zambia. Data available through agreement with national meteorological agency.	National coverage at high spatial and temporal resolution (4km and 10 daily)	In near real-time therefore suitable for EWS. Data aggregated over 10 days and available 1-3 days after collection. No operational temperature monitoring products.
Sea Surface Temperatures (SSTs) in specific regions measured by remote sensing and or buoy.	Global producing Centers.	Provides an indication of likely anomalies in rainfall 0-6 months ahead of the season; and an indication of region wide warming. Particularly skilful in ENSO years.	Data from one region may not capture all predictive aspects of the climate of a location	Target SST region known to be teleconnected to regional rainfall and temperatures	Available in near-real time on monthly basis. Strong indicator of seasonal climate in some regions (e.g. those affected by ENSO). Suitable for EWS.
Seasonal climate forecasts based on statistical and dynamical models of climate system driven by sea-surface temperatures	Regional Outlook For a, Global producing Centers including IRI.	Provides an indication of likely anomalies in rainfall and region wide warming 1-6 months ahead of the season. Particularly skilful in ENSO years.	Large spatial scale, relevant for some regions in some seasons.	Pan African	Available in near real time on three month basis with 1-6 month lead times. Suitable for EWS.

TABLE 3 METEOROLOGICAL DATA (RAINFALL, TEMPERATURE, HUMIDITY) CHARACTERISTICS AND SOURCES THAT ARE PUBLICLY AVAILABLE FOR MALARIA CLIMATE ANALYSIS AND EARLY WARNING SYSTEMS. DATA CAN BE ACCESSED FROM THE IRI DATA LIBRARY [HTTP://IRIDL.LDEO.COLUMBIA.EDU/](http://iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu/)

⁹ Moderate-resolution imaging spectroradiometer

¹⁰ European Center for Medium Range Weather Forecasting second generation reanalysis data

¹¹ European Center for Medium Range Weather Forecasting third generation reanalysis data

¹² NASA reanalysis data

¹³ iri.columbia.edu/ENACTS

	Time	Operational availability	Skill ¹⁴	Relevance for use in vector-borne disease control
Weather forecasts	Hours up to 2 weeks	National meteorological service forecasts Global forecasts from international centers (e.g. ECMWF)	Skill often unknown as many developing country meteorological services do not verify their forecasts, but in Africa few countries have capacities to skilfully predict the weather beyond 2 days. Extending forecasts to 5 or even 10 days may be possible in some areas. Global weather forecasts are often poorly calibrated for local use.	Short term weather forecasts give little additional time for a vector-borne disease early warning system although they might provide valuable information on extreme events that may impact the health system more broadly.
Seasonal climate forecasts	Season	Available from some national meteorological services, from WMO Regional Climate Centres and global producers (e.g. IRI)	Skilful for some regions of the world and some seasons. Skill is greatest during El Nino or La Nina events.	Can add months to early warning system based on monitored rainfall and temperature in regions and seasons where predictability is high.
Decadal forecasts	2-9 years	Experimental forecasts only https://www.wcrp-climate.org/dcp-overview	Poor skill at local levels. Some skill exists for temperature over oceans and some land areas, but precipitation skill is generally poor. Skilful predictions mostly only possible in areas with strong long-term trends; interannual and decadal variability is not well predicted.	Highly desirable for planning purposes diseases but not available operationally at present. However, where decadal variability is not strong temperature may follow long term trend.
Multi-decadal scenarios	10-30 years	Global and regional uninitialized projections developed for the IPCC assessments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global projections available from the Coordinated Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP)¹⁵ Regional projections available from Coordinated Regional Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX)¹⁶ 	Not suitable for direct use in local decision-making. No skill assessments available, only general model evaluations. Model capabilities vary by region, season, scale and variable. Models perform better for temperature than precipitation, and at large spatial scales. Climate and weather variability has not been thoroughly assessed on all timescales but long-term averages often better than short term variability, particularly weather extremes. Not possible to quantitatively determine the most likely scenario among those available.	Highly desirable for planning purposes diseases but not available operationally at present. However, where decadal variability is not strong temperature may follow long term trend.
Very long-term scenarios	Century			Temperature trends, especially in the absence of strong decadal variability, may provide valuable information for development of malaria eradication strategy. Rainfall scenarios are highly uncertain but indicate drying regions in the extra-tropics (e.g. southern and northern Africa). Timescale largely outside of operational vector-borne disease decision-time frames.

¹⁴ Skill is measured by the extent to which a forecast outperforms another reference forecast strategy, most commonly taken to be the average climate (called the 'climatology')

¹⁵ <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/cmip5/>

¹⁶ <http://cordex.org/>

TABLE 4 AVAILABILITY AND UTILITY OF WEATHER AND CLIMATE FORECASTS FOR USE IN VECTOR-BORNE DISEASE CONTROL

CLIMATE PREDICTION SKILL

DECADAL FORECAST SKILL

FIGURE 13 MEAN SQUARE SKILL SCORE (MSSS) FOR 2-9 YEAR FORECASTS OF AVERAGE PRECIPITATION (LEFT COLUMN) AND TEMPERATURE (RIGHT COLUMN). TOP ROW: SKILL DIFFERENCE BETWEEN INITIALISED AND UNINITIALISED HINDCASTS, MIDDLE ROW: INITIALISED HINDCASTS; BOTTOM ROW: UNINITIALISED HINDCASTS. (SEE [HTTP://CLIVAR-DPWG.IRI.COLUMBIA.EDU/](http://clivar-dpwg.iri.columbia.edu/) FOR MORE INFORMATION INCLUDING INDIVIDUAL MODELS, SKILL METRICS, LEAD TIMES AND EVALUATION OPTIONS).

SEASONAL FORECAST SKILL

FIGURE 14 GENERALISED ROC SCORE (A MEASURE OF FORECAST DISCRIMINATION) FOR THREE-MONTH SEASONAL FORECASTS OF (A, C) PRECIPITATION AND (B, D) TEMPERATURE DURING TWO SEASONS: JULY-SEPTEMBER (A, B) AND OCTOBER-NOVEMBER (C, D). LEAD-TIMES OF ALL FORECASTS ARE 3.5 MONTHS. SEE [HTTP://IRI.COLUMBIA.EDU/OUR-EXPERTISE/CLIMATE/FORECASTS/VERIFICATION/](http://iri.columbia.edu/our-expertise/climate/forecasts/verification/) FOR OTHER SEASONS, FORECAST LEAD TIMES AND METRICS OF SKILL.

CLIMATE DRIVERS OF REGIONAL PRECIPITATION AND TEMPERATURE

FIGURE 15 HISTORICAL PROBABILITY (GIVEN IN PERCENTILE) OF SEASONALLY AVERAGED MONTHLY RAINFALL AND TEMPERATURE FALLING WITHIN A PARTICULAR THIRD (“TERCILE”) OF THE 1981-2015 DISTRIBUTION IN EACH COUNTRY, CONDITIONAL ON THE OCCURRENCE OF EL NIÑO DURING THAT SAME SEASON. TOP ROW: PROBABILITY OF EL NIÑO-ASSOCIATED ABOVE-NORMAL TEMPERATURE FOR (A) JUL-SEP AND (B) OCT-DEC. MIDDLE ROW: PROBABILITY OF EL NIÑO-ASSOCIATED BELOW-NORMAL RAINFALL FOR (C) JUL-SEP AND (D) OCT-DEC. BOTTOM ROW: PROBABILITY OF EL NIÑO-ASSOCIATED ABOVE-NORMAL RAINFALL FOR (E) JUL-SEP AND (F) OCT-DEC. SEE [HTTP://IRIDL.LDEO.COLUMBIA.EDU/MAPROOM/ENSO/CLIMATE_IMPACTS/ENSO_PRCP_PROB_ONI.HTML](http://iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu/maproom/ENSO/CLIMATE_IMPACTS/ENSO_PRCP_PROB_ONI.HTML) FOR OTHER SEASONS, TERCILES AND REGIONS AND FOR MORE INFORMATION ON THE METHODOLOGY.

FIGURE 16 AS IN FIGURE 13, BUT CONDITIONAL ON THE OCCURRENCE OF LA NIÑA. SEE [HTTP://IRIDL.LDEO.COLUMBIA.EDU/MAPROOM/ENSO/CLIMATE_IMPACTS/ENSO_PRCB_PROB_ONI.HTML](http://iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu/maproom/ENSO/CLIMATE_IMPACTS/ENSO_PRCB_PROB_ONI.HTML) FOR OTHER SEASONS, TERCILES AND REGIONS AND FOR MORE INFORMATION ON THE METHODOLOGY.

FIGURE 17 HISTORICAL PROBABILITY (GIVEN IN PERCENTILE) OF SEASONALLY AVERAGED MONTHLY RAINFALL FALLING WITHIN THE UPPER (WET) ONE-THIRD ("TERCILE") OF THE 1983-2015 DISTRIBUTION IN THE COUNTRY GIVEN THE OCCURRENCE OF EL NIÑO/LA NIÑA DURING THAT SAME SEASON. A DRY MASK IS USED WHENEVER THE SUM TOTAL OF RAINFALL IS ≤ 10 MM FOR EACH THREE-MONTH SEASON. A) DEPICTS THE PROBABILITY OF EL NIÑO-ASSOCIATED ABOVE NORMAL RAINFALL FOR OCT-DEC (NOTE THE SEVERE IMPACT IN EASTERN EQUATORIAL AFRICA) AND B) DEPICTS EL NIÑO-ASSOCIATED BELOW NORMAL RAINFALL IMPACT FOR JUL-SEP (NOTE THE SEVERE IMPACT IN ETHIOPIA) C) THE LA NIÑA-ASSOCIATED ABOVE NORMAL RAINFALL FOR DEC - FEB (NOTE THE SEVERE IMPACT IN SOUTHERN AFRICA) AND D) EL NIÑO-ASSOCIATED ABOVE NORMAL RAINFALL FOR MAR-MAY (NOTE THE ABSENCE OF IMPACT FOR THIS MAIN RAINY SEASON IN EASTERN AFRICA).

TIMESCALE DECOMPOSITIONS OF RAINFALL AND TEMPERATURE IN SELECTED REGIONS OF THE WORLD

AFRICA

FIGURE 18 TIMESCALE DECOMPOSITION FOR ANNUAL PRECIPITATION (A–C) AND TEMPERATURE (D–F). EACH MAP SHOWS THE PERCENT OF TOTAL VARIANCE IN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION/TEMPERATURE WHICH CAN BE EXPLAINED BY THE LONG-TERM TREND (A, D) AND BY DECADAL (B, E) AND INTERANNUAL VARIABILITY (C, F). GRID POINTS IN WHITE INDICATE PLACES WHERE INSUFFICIENT DATA WERE AVAILABLE FOR ROBUST ANALYSIS. THE BLACK BOXES ARE THE DOMAINS USED FOR THE TIME-SERIES ANALYSES SHOWN IN FIGURE 19. SEE [HTTP://MBELL.MAPROOMDEV.IRI.COLUMBIA.EDU/MAPROOM/GLOBAL/TIME_SCALES/INDEX.HTML](http://mbell.maproomdev.iri.columbia.edu/maproom/global/time_scales/index.html) FOR MORE INFORMATION ON THE METHODOLOGY.

FIGURE 19 TIMESCALE DECOMPOSITION FOR ANNUAL PRECIPITATION (A, C, E) AND TEMPERATURE (B, D, F) AVERAGED OVER THE BOXES SHOWN IN DIFFERENT AFRICAN REGIONS IN FIGURE 18. THE BLACK LINE SHOWS THE RAW ANNUAL DATA (PRECIPITATION (LEFT) OR TEMPERATURE (RIGHT)). THE LONG-TERM TREND IS SHOWN IN RED AND THE DECADAL AND INTERANNUAL COMPONENTS OF VARIABILITY ARE SHOWN IN GREEN AND BLUE, RESPECTIVELY. THE TOTAL VARIANCE IN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION/TEMPERATURE IS EQUAL OR VERY CLOSE TO THE SUM OF VARIANCE FROM THE LONG-TERM TREND, DECADAL AND INTERANNUAL COMPONENTS. SEE [HTTP://MBELL.MAPROOMDEV.IRI.COLUMBIA.EDU/MAPROOM/GLOBAL/TIME_SCALES/INDEX.HTML](http://mbell.maproomdev.iri.columbia.edu/maproom/global/time_scales/index.html) FOR MORE INFORMATION ON THE METHODOLOGY.

LATIN AMERICA

FIGURE 20 AS FOR FIGURE 18 BUT FOR LATIN AMERICA.

FIGURE 21 AS FOR FIGURE 17 BUT FOR THE REGION SHOWN BY THE BLACK BOX IN FIGURE 20. THE PERCENTAGES SHOWN IN THE LEGEND GIVE THE PERCENT OF TOTAL VARIANCE IN ANNUAL RAINFALL/TEMPERATURE EXPLAINED BY EACH COMPONENT OF VARIABILITY.

SOUTH ASIA

FIGURE 22 AS FOR FIGURE 18 BUT FOR SOUTH ASIA.

FIGURE 23 AS FOR FIGURE 19 BUT FOR THE ENTIRE SOUTH ASIA DOMAIN DEPICTED IN FIGURE 22. THE PERCENTAGES SHOWN IN THE LEGEND GIVE THE PERCENT OF TOTAL VARIANCE IN ANNUAL RAINFALL/TEMPERATURE EXPLAINED BY EACH COMPONENT OF VARIABILITY.